

FUTURE MIGRATION
SCENARIOS FOR EUROPE

Case Study

SENEGAL

Drivers and Trajectories of Migration to Europe

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ISBN 978-91-8001-074-0

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.8223962

Funded by the EU Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant ID 870649.

Cover photo: Mhrezaa/Unsplash.com

Layout: Kotryna Juskaite

List of abbreviations and acronyms

ADB African Development Bank
ANPEJ National Agency for the Promotion of Youth Employment
ANSD National Agency for Statistics and Demography
AU African Union
CIRAD French Agricultural Research Centre for International Development
ENDA Third World
ENDA Perspectives Dialogues Politiques
EU European Union
FAO Food and Agriculture Organization
IFAD International Fund for Agricultural Development
IOM International Organisation for Migration
IOM-GMDAC International Organization for Migration's Global Migration Data Analysis Centre
IPAR - Initiative Prospective Agricole et Rural
IPCC Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IRD Institute of Research for Development
JRC Joint Research Centre
LPS Sector policy letter
LPSEDD Sector policy letter on the environment and sustainable development
MAESE Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Senegalese Abroad
MEDD Ministry of the Environment and Sustainable Development
ONU United Nations Organization
PANAUDIT Pan African Audit
PSE Plan for an Emerging Senegal
PSO Strategic and Operational Plan
RGPHAE General Census of Population and Housing, Agriculture and Livestock
UNDESA United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division
USAID US Agency for International Development
WB World Bank

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1. Introduction

As mentioned in the introduction, Senegal has been a country of migration since the 1970s (15 million inhabitants/over 2.5 million diaspora members). Although most Senegalese emigrate within Africa, 41% of all Senegalese emigrants live in Europe.

This report is drawn up on the basis of research carried out in Senegal between 2020 and 2021 and is one of the outputs of the FUME research project. Its objective is twofold:

- to illustrate the main environmental, demographic, socio-cultural, economic and geopolitical characteristics and patterns that, from the local to the regional and international level, shape internal and international Senegalese migration trajectories;
- to analyse the results of the research undertaken in the Dakar region, including 30 in-depth interviews with potential migrants and 6 semi-structured interviews with migration experts.

While the context of analysis has been examined through interviews with key experts from different professional backgrounds (academic scholars, representatives of national and international institutions, members of humanitarian organizations or associations of the third sector), the majority of the interviews were aimed at collecting the experiences of migrants or “would-be migrants” to Europe. The interviewees were defined, according to their different period of arrival in Dakar from rural or secondary urban areas, as: “*newcomers*” (arrived in the last 5 years), “*long stayers*” (settled for 5 up to 10 years) and “*settled migrants*” (over 10 years). However, unlike the initial project plan, as a result of the people interviewed, the information collected was organized according to two categories: *newcomers* and *settled migrants*. The research does not account for the migration motivation patterns of natives of Dakar. The aim of the presentation of the research results is to discuss the qualitative evidence and conform the analyses with the observations on the other migration countries of origin (Tunisia, Iraq and Ukraine) in the reports drawn up by the other three research teams. The report is structured in three parts. The introductory part sets out the objectives and justifications of the study, followed by the presentation of the main theoretical and methodological approaches adopted. The second part of the report is devoted to the presentation of the context of analysis. It is organized around six chapters which provide an updated overview of the country.

The first chapter of this second part illustrates the environmental characteristics of Senegal and describes the main changes in terms of population mobility dynamics at the national and regional levels. The second chapter consists of a demographic description of the past and present situation of the population, with particular attention to the main trends that are likely to influence the composition of future demographic patterns. The third chapter focuses on the socio-cultural characteristics that shape the composition and profile of the Senegalese population. The key topics taken into consideration are the role of education, social networks (e.g., family ties, religious, cultural and migration networks) and the socio-cultural roots of the propensity to move. The fourth chapter provides an overview of Senegal’s economic context, limiting its focus to regional development patterns. The fifth chapter provides a brief overview of the political context in Senegal. Particular attention is paid to geopolitical dynamics and political divisions, as well as current conditions concerning security and respect for human rights. The focus of the next chapter

is on presenting the main migration policies implemented at the national level, aimed at internal mobility and international mobility to the European Union. In this sixth chapter, a final section is dedicated to the presentation of the main migration patterns in the Dakar region, the selected city of the research.

The third part of the report focuses on analysing the information provided by the interviewees, potential migrants and key experts.

Objectives and justification of the study: Senegal and the Dakar region

The decision of *whether* and *where* to migrate depends largely on interlinked local, regional, national and transnational factors in the places of origin and destination and is therefore insufficiently captured in the existing migration statistics and scenarios focusing on the national level. The decision is also made according to individual and/or collective choices. Likewise, the effects of migration have the most direct impact at the local level, both on the places that migrants leave and, on the ones, where they choose to settle. The objective of the qualitative research of the FUME project regarding migrants' origin countries is to take forward the analysis and to fill in gaps in the existing knowledge on the different aspects of migration propensity, intentions and decisions.

Located at the westernmost point of Africa in the Atlantic Ocean and about 1,000 miles north of the equator, Senegal is at the same time an important country both of origin and destination in the West Africa region, as well as a country of transit migration and emigration towards higher-income countries. Sène et al. (2019) underline the complexity of the migratory dynamics in Senegal. The available data indicate that Africa remains the main destination continent for international emigrants from Senegal, but that today Europe, South America, North America and more recently China are also part of the Senegalese migration field. In fact, Senegalese migration has experienced significant changes since the early 1990s, marked by a more systematic orientation of migration flows to the North but also by the increasing participation of women in international migration (to southern Europe and the USA). According to the Planning and Statistics Department (2004), 54% of the Senegalese who went abroad between 1999 and 2004 chose to settle in Europe (46%) and the USA (8%), against 44% who settled in Africa (14% in the UEMOA area and 30% in the rest of the continent). These numbers probably vary over time and depending on the statistical information available.

Abel and Cohen (2019) provide estimates of bilateral migration flows between all countries for the five-year periods between 1990 and 2015 based on data on international migration stocks and flows using different algorithms. There are three groups of methods for estimating bilateral migration flows based on changes in migrant stocks: methods using the differences in successive bilateral stocks of migrants, methods estimating migration flow rates, and methods based on global demographic accounting using bilateral stocks of migrants, and births and deaths. Please refer to the publication by Abel and Cohen (2019) for any technical questions. Table 1 presents selected results for Senegal, all of which are relatively high estimates referring to five-year intervals.

Table 1. 5-year emigration & immigration flows according to different estimation methods, Senegal
Source: Abel and Cohen, 2019

	Five-year emigration and immigration flows and net migration rates (per 1,000)				
	1990–1995	1995–2000	2000–2005	2005–2010	2010–2015
Emigration					
Migration rate method (Dennett, 2016)	137,600	110,500	122,900	164,500	160,900
Demographic accounting (Abel, 2018)	161,500	227,900	208,900	239,000	244,300
Demographic accounting (Azose and Raftery, 2018)	221,100	287,700	273,300	311,800	324,200
Immigration					
Migration rate method (Dennett, 2016)	87,100	77,100	61,900	70,600	62,200
Demographic accounting (Abel, 2018)	84,600	400	6,400	21,000	30,200
Demographic accounting (Azose and Raftery, 2018)	144,200	60,100	70,800	93,700	110,200
Net migration rates (per 1,000)					
Migration rate method (Dennett, 2016)	-6,7	-3,8	-6,2	-8,5	-7,8
Demographic accounting (Abel, 2018)	-10.2	-26.2	-20.7	-19.7	-16.9
Demographic accounting (Azose and Raftery, 2018)	-10.2	-26.2	-20.7	-19.7	-16.9

Table 1 shows an increase in emigration flows over the last 30 years. For the period 2010–2015, Senegalese emigration is estimated at between 161,000 and 325,000 migrants. There appears to be no clear trend in immigration and it is estimated at between 30,000 and 110,000 migrants for the period 2010–2015. The other methods employed by Abel and Cohen (2019), not reported here, generally lead to considerably lower numbers of migrants. The net migration rate estimates are also shown considering the average population estimates for Senegal for the five-year periods (7,526,000, 8,690,000, 9,798,000, 11,090,000 and 12,678,000 respectively). It is not a surprise that

all of the estimation methods see a population loss for Senegal due to international migratory movements over the last decades. Whereas the migration rate method results in a lower population loss, the demographic accounting methods estimate net migration at 1% for the period 1990–1995, increasing in the following period to 2.6% and decreasing slightly to reach 1.7% in 2010–2015.

The main destination countries are, on the one hand, the high-income countries of France, Italy and Spain, as well as other European countries and the USA, and, on the other, neighbouring countries or African countries in general such as Congo, Ivory Coast, Gabon, Gambia, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Mauritania, Mali, Sierra Leone, etc. Estimates of bilateral migration flows between Senegal and other countries vary according to the method of estimation and the observation period. At the root of this uncertainty is the absence of comprehensive and reliable migration statistics.

The 2013 population census reported only 164,901 Senegalese who emigrated during the previous five years (IOM, 2018). According to this statistical source, about 46% lived in Africa and 45% in Europe. For the end of 2015, EC-KCMD (Urso et al. 2019) report estimates of 544,800 immigrants (3.6% of the Senegalese population), 23,000 refugees and 266,700 Senegalese emigrants.

Most recently, IOM-GMDAC (2021) report estimates that put the 2021 mid-year total number of international migrants at 274,900 or 1.6% of the population of Senegal and the total number of Senegalese emigrants at 693,800.

Recently, special attention has been given to the irregular migration that has emerged in the past decades (Sène et al., 2019). Whereas in the past the central Mediterranean route played a major role, today the western African route is more important. There are two of these routes: the mixed land and sea route of Mauritania, Morocco and Spain, and the so-called boat migration along the sea route to the Canary Islands (degli Uberti, 2014). The varying importance of different transit routes and countries of destination attests to the vitality and flexibility of Senegalese emigration patterns. Transit migrants and emigrants adapt rapidly to the changing economic and political conditions and available migration routes.

This short overview about the available numbers shows how also in the case of Senegal it is difficult it is to establish well-founded statistical bases for past and present migration stocks and flows.

The Senegal field research reported here was conducted between January and March 2021, in the urban and peri-urban area of the so-called Dakar region, the capital of Senegal. The choice of Dakar is mainly tied to the important role that the Senegalese capital plays as a crossroads in both internal and international trajectories of Senegalese migration. Internal migration has been increasing for 10 years, particularly towards the regions of Dakar and the region of Diourbel, which are respectively the economic and religious centres of the country (Ba et al., 2017: 16).

2. The context of the analysis

2.1 Environmental conditions

Country-level environmental characteristics

The climate in Senegal is largely shaped by a great spatial and temporal variability in precipitation (WFP, 2012) along with cooler temperatures during the wet season, alternating with a warm climate in the rest of the year (USAID, 2015). The rainy season (*hivernage*), which usually lasts from June to September (Fall et al., 2006; Funk et al., 2012; Rust et al., 2013), alternates with the dry period (*saison sèche*) when both seeding and harvesting take place.

Due to the geographical expanse of Senegal, the northern, southern, eastern and western zones of the country are characterized by different climatic conditions (Gueye et al., 2007). The influence of the continental, oceanic (Fall et al., 2006) as well as Sudano-Guinean climate (Gueye et al., 2007) shapes the Senegalese territory, ranging from moist tropical conditions in the western African zones to the arid Sahara Desert in the north. To some extent, these features provide an explanation for the different ecosystems and production systems that lead to seasonal and inter-regional migrations.

During the last decades, West Africa has experienced a warming phase with an annual increase in temperature ranging between +0.3 and +1°C (IPCC, 2013 in Sylla et al., 2016; Lo et al., 2014). This is also confirmed by the World Bank, according to which between 1961 and 2000 the region experienced an increase in the number of warm spells and declines in mean annual precipitation (World Bank, 2019). In particular, with a 0.9°C rise in the mean annual temperature since 1960 – an average rate of 0.2°C per decade (World Bank, 2019) – and with approximately 46% of its territory classified as semi-arid, Senegal is especially vulnerable to the effects of global warming, having experienced an increase in average monthly temperatures from 1961–1990 (figure 1) to 1991–2016 (figure 2).

Figure 1. Average Monthly Temperature of Senegal for 1961-1990.

Source: World Bank, 2019

Figure 2. Average Monthly Temperature of Senegal for 1991-2016.

Source: World Bank, 2019

Senegal, which ranks 13th of all countries in terms of the absolute increase in population exposed to droughts if global warming reaches 2°C, has experienced a significant decrease in rainfall during the wet season in the last decades (World Bank, 2019). The region is prone to climate variability, with unstable and irregular rainfall, and patterns ranging between 200 mm and 600 mm with coefficients of variation ranging from 15% to 30% (Kandji et al., 2006; Fall et al., 2006; Funk et al., 2012), and has suffered recurrent droughts, for example: 1972–1973, 1982–1984 and recently in the 1990s.

In some cases, these phenomena have been attributed to the natural variability of the climate. Although there is no doubt as to the major impact of drought on the population of Senegal, particularly in the arid and semi-arid Sahelian territories in the northern regions of the country, the great variability of past climate patterns could make it difficult to obtain accurate projections (Gueye et al., 2007) and could also suggest that these patterns are not related to global climate change (Noblet et al., 2018; Chesnier and Margaglio, 2019). However, similarly to the catastrophic drought years of the 1970s, 1980s and 1990s, the current downward estimates suggest further possible reductions in rainfall by 2050 which, coupled with a 2°C to 5°C rise in the maximum and minimum temperatures (USAID, 2014), will arguably lead to more extreme droughts. This will be of particular concern for northern Senegal, an area that is highly susceptible to desertification. Unlike the past drought periods, these projections of severe change are certainly more related to the effects of global climate change. With the considerable unpredictability of mean precipitation (Christensen et al., 2013) and extreme events, such as desert locust infestations causing significant crop losses throughout West Africa (Seneviratne et al., 2012), uncertainty remains high.

In terms of livelihoods and health security, the Senegalese population is increasingly vulnerable to climate change not only due to the weak capacity of the state and general financial constraints but primarily due to the heavy reliance on rainfed agriculture (Castells-Quintana et al., 2015), which is the backbone of the rural economy, employing 77% of the Senegalese workforce and accounting for 12% of the national GDP (Funk et al., 2012). Particularly hit by climate change is smallholder agriculture, already stressed by land overexploitation and degradation.

The main consequences of the droughts of the 1970s and 1980s were the reduction in plant coverage and a gradual degradation of land productivity, which in turn led to a reduction in agricultural potential, directly impacting on the income of the population (IRD-IPAR, 2017). In 2013, about 22% of the 13.5 million Senegalese were living on 13% of the country's degraded land (IRD-IPAR, 2017). For 2030, a 5% loss in the average crop yield is forecasted (Hallegatte et al., 2015). This great loss can only partially be attributed to climate change

against a background of what is still a “highly underdeveloped sector characterized by (1) an almost total dependence on rainfall, (2) low use of external inputs, (3) absence of mechanization and (4) poor linkages to markets” (Kandji et al., 2006: 1).

Food security is further threatened by declining fish stocks. Fishery, like agriculture, is susceptible to the impacts of climate change. In Senegal, fishing employs 17% of the workforce, contributes 2.5% to the GDP and provides one of the main sources of animal protein in the Senegalese diet. Already stressed from overfishing, the sector is expected to be negatively impacted by climate change as rising surface water temperatures and ocean acidification alter the reproduction and migration of species. This in turn threatens the biodiversity and the livelihoods and incomes of approximately 600,000 persons working directly or indirectly in the Senegalese fishing sector (FAO, 2008). So, climate change obviously threatens the Senegalese population’s supply of fishery products. According to the recent World Fish Centre report (Allison et al. 2009), Senegal’s economy is “highly vulnerable” to the effects of global warming on fish stocks, and has a limited capacity to adapt, triggering increased and diversified mobility patterns. Despite all of this, fishing communities have received scant attention in the political sphere.

Recent projections drawn from the INFORM Index for Risk Management show that Senegal is seriously vulnerable to coastal erosion, flooding and the salinization of fresh water sources, which will result from and be compounded by rising sea levels (INFORM, 2019). A sea level rise is projected to cause the contamination of fresh water supplies through saltwater intrusion. This will exacerbate pre-existing issues of water scarcity. Nonetheless, coastal erosion generally results in a gradual deterioration in the living conditions of the populations in these areas. In coastal areas, the infrastructure, including 74% of buildings, is at risk from sea level rise-induced coastal erosion and inundation. Almost every major coastal city in Senegal is being affected by rapid and pervasive erosion (due to both climate conditions and human activity), leading to losses of physical and financial assets. The entire coast south of Dakar is particularly hit by marine erosion, with effects on the dwellings of local populations and tourist facilities (e.g., in the Petite Côte, Îles du Saloum and Casamance regions). The encroachment of the sea upon the land has also considerably accelerated the degradation of the environment and natural ecosystems of the Langue de Barbarie (the region of Saint-Louis). This phenomenon has been accentuated by the impact of climate change on mangroves, especially in the region of Sine-Saloum. Mangroves are a vital coastal resource as they protect the coastline by moderating the impact of storms and waves. Furthermore, they stabilize sand and soils, cycle nutrients, absorb and break down waste products, provide a habitat for wildlife and maintain biodiversity.

The environmental framework of coastal erosion is also marked by different types of pollution, for example, of surface water caused by the discharge of household and industrial waste (ANSD and IOM, 2018: 60).

At the same time, flooding has become a recurrent phenomenon in Senegal; according to various estimates, it affects between 150,000 and 300,000 people per year (OCHA, 2013). This phenomenon concerns both urban and rural areas and it particularly affects the regions of Dakar, Fatick, Kaffrine, Kaolack, Saint-Louis, Thiès, Kolda and Ziguinchor. Often the populations who dwell in these areas are already living in vulnerable and precarious conditions. Flooding in urban areas has been exacerbated by the illegal and unsuitable occupation of “non aedificandi” (non-building) zones. Generally, the majority of those affected live in conditions of extreme poverty and precariousness, and often end up losing their homes and property (ANSD and IOM, 2018: 60).

To different degrees, these often intertwined environmental transformations impact on the mobilities of the Senegalese population. Although statistics on the migration processes fuelled by coastal erosion are scarce, evidence from qualitative studies shows that the movement of individuals, which can also lead to family migration, is an increasingly frequent phenomenon (ANSD and IOM, 2018).

Risks posed by desertification, the massive loss of agricultural production, overexploitation of forest and fish stocks, unavailability of water, soil erosion, the reduction of organic matter and loss of biodiversity, combined

with youth unemployment and persistent poverty, represent major development challenges (Kälin, 2010; Sylla et al., 2016; Kandji et al., 2006) and can lead to an increase in migration in the short, medium and long term.

Within the political framework of the “Great Green Wall for the Sahara and the Sahel” (Grande Muraille Verte pour le Sahara et le Sahel)¹, in 2014, Senegal adopted a new development model to accelerate its progress towards “emerging market” status. This strategy, entitled the “Plan Sénégal Émergent” (PSE), now constitutes the reference for economic and social policy in the medium and long term. The PSE acknowledges the green economy as a means to meet basic social needs and achieve sustainable development. The PSE is supposed to transform the country into an “emerging country” by 2035. As far as environmental issues are concerned, the strategic plan of the Ministry of the Environment and Sustainable Development (MEDD) was defined and put into operation in the Policy Letter for the Environment and Sustainable Development Sector (LPSEDD) 2016-2020.

The document sets out two strategic axes in order to achieve the overall objective. The first specific objective is to integrate the principles of sustainable development into public policies, namely, management of the living environment and promotion of livelihoods as well as the resilience of vulnerable groups and their modes of production and consumption. The second specific objective is to reduce environmental degradation (e.g., by fighting against deforestation which is affecting 91% of the Tambacounda region and the land degradation linked to bush fires), to protect the biodiversity and promote the management of protected areas, and to fight against pollutants and the harmful effects of climate change (e.g., the erosion of the sandy coasts in the Petite Côte and Casamance regions and the coastal erosion of the Langue de Barbarie peninsula, in the neighbourhood of Saint-Louis, which separates the ocean from the final section of the Senegal River) (ANSD, 2019).

Environmental changes and mobility dynamics

Several pieces of evidence demonstrate that some of the Senegalese mobility patterns are inextricably intertwined with transformations of the natural environment in various regions of the country. One such example is the 1970s drought period in the northern regions (Gueye et al., 2007), marked by a massive displacement of populations from the interior of the country, which had become arid, to two main destinations: Dakar and the major fishing centres. Others migrated en masse to the south of the country, particularly to the central region (Fatick and Kaolack) and Casamance where rainfall and the soil conditions allow higher agricultural yields. These observations are based on lifetime migration patterns obtained by comparing the places of birth and places of residence of persons registered in the 2013 population census, whereas the information reported in figure 3 refers to the differences in residence one year before and at the date of the population census.

¹ Launched in 2007 by the African Union, the Great Green Wall for the Sahara and the Sahel is an African initiative, implemented in more than 20 countries and aimed at combatting the increasing desertification, to restore 100 million hectares of currently degraded land and transform the lives of millions of people in the Sahel regions by creating a mosaic of green and productive landscapes across North Africa. Since its official start, in Senegal 11.4 million trees have been planted and 25,000 hectares of degraded land restored, mainly in three regions of the country: Louga, Matam and Tambacounda.

Figure 3. Annual movements in the Senegal River valley, Saint-Louis region.
Source: ANSD, 2014

While the visible climate changes will certainly play an increasing role in shaping future migratory dynamics, it is hardly possible to detach the influence of slow-onset environmental changes from political, economic, social and demographic factors (Black et al., 2011) or from the decision-making processes at individual and collective levels. Thus, different patterns of environment-induced migration (e.g., internal, cross-border, international) emerge as a socially constructed phenomenon and only one of the possible adaptation options (Henry et al., 2003). "It is largely the socio-economic context that makes such [environmental] events so catastrophic, by restricting people's ability to rely on well-tested strategies of local diversification of activities, both within the agricultural sector and in the non-farm sector" (Tacoli, 2011: 28-29).

The link between environmental and climate changes and migration still remains a complex issue to analyse, not least owing to the difficulties in carrying out observations and monitoring activities (Beyani, 2013). Nonetheless, the complexity of establishing the correlation between international migration and environmental changes is further amplified by the fact that the features of sub-Saharan migration do not often appear to be a response to ecological crisis but rather to a mix of non-climatic stressors (social, economic, political and cultural), such as agricultural expansion, new policies (ANSD and IOM, 2018), overgrazing and population growth (Mertz et al., 2011; Lo et al., 2014). Also contributing to the phenomenon is the fact that rural areas often lack job opportunities and adequate infrastructure with regard to administration, sanitation as well as cultural and educational institutions (Pigué, 2008; Véron, 2012). The slow and gradual climatic and environmental changes that have an important role in accelerating and exacerbating poverty do not emerge as the key causal factor but rather a factor aggravating vulnerability and triggering mobility. In this sense, they strongly influence decisions to migrate, but are not the sole, main cause (Touré Thiam and Crowley, 2014).

As noticeably pointed out by Véron (2012), contrary to straightforward arguments that envisage future migratory scenarios shaped by a cause-effect relationship between environmental changes and international migration outside the African continent, mobility linked to the consequences of environmental changes is generally internal and mainly takes place within the country, from one region to another, from the countryside to the cities. The most frequent result of drought periods is to increase internal, short-term or circular patterns

of mobility. Based on her research in the Senegalese locations of Gandiol, Ngueye-Ngueye, Ross-Bethio and Oourossogui, Tacoli (2009) notes that internal migration caused by environmental changes does not necessarily imply abandoning lands or displacement to urban areas but rather causes temporary or circular movements towards Dakar and secondary cities: Thiès, Diourbel (the second economic centre of the country) and Touba (the capital of the Murid Brotherhood in the Diourbel region and second largest city in Senegal) (Tacoli, 2009; USAID, 2014). Within this perspective, rather than being a failure to adapt, exodus or abandonment, individual and collective migration is to be considered an adaptation strategy aimed at protecting and ensuring the survival and continuity of the socio-economic context of the area of origin (Lalou and Delauney, 2017) and, at the same time, a way of pursuing aspirations for a better life (Some, 2009: 65).

Internal movements measured as lifetime migration (or migration *durée de vie*)² are mostly tied to historical patterns of seasonal migration from rural to urban or between urban centres during the dry season (this seasonal migration is called “noorane”) which have developed in parallel to the “navétanes”: the seasonal movement of young men who leave the city to work as farm labourers or shepherds in rural areas. Now the noorane has become an increasingly long-term migration, leading to the development of slums within and around the cities: these spontaneous neighbourhoods are the primary destination of the rural exodus (Lo et al., 2014) because traditional ties remain strong in these places. In Senegal, the rate of urbanization increased from 23% in 1960, to 40% in 2000 and 48% in 2019 (UNDESA, 2019b). In particular, according to RGPHE data from 2013, the Dakar region concentrates nearly a quarter of the Senegalese urban population (23.2%) within just 0.3% of the area of the country (ANSD, 2014); 43% of internal migrants, equal to 820,000 individuals, are concentrated in the urban area of the capital (ANSD, 2014). However, unlike in the past, it is important to point out that today internal migration towards Dakar is also, if not mostly (Duboz et al., 2011), of urban origin (see figure 3 and table 2); moreover, recent migrants have a higher educational level and are on average older than earlier migrants. While women migrate most often for marriage, men increasingly move in order to pursue their studies, even if the search for more profitable job opportunities is still the main driving force (Duboz et al., 2011). The Diourbel region counts nearly 295,000 lifetime migrants and the Thiès region 241,000, 13% of the influx of internal migrants (IFAD, 2015), also owing to the saturation of the Dakar peninsula and the general improvement of the road network (figures 4 and 5) (Ba et al., 2017).

Figure 4. Importance of lifetime internal migration (*durée de vie*) according to destination region. Source: Adapted from IFAD, 2015: 4.

² According to ANSD (2014), “migration *durée de vie*” is defined as migration in which the current place of residence is different from the place of birth.

Figure 5. Migration flows between regions.
Source: Ba et al., 2017: 33.

Variables	Categories	N° interviewed	%
Place of birth	Main cities	104	40.6
	Secondary cities	75	29.3
	Rural area	77	30.1
Age of settling in Dakar	0-19 years	126	49.2
	20-29 years	92	35.9
	30 years and over	38	14.8
Date of settlement in Dakar	≤ 1969	34	13.3
	1970-1979	32	12.5
	1980-1989	47	18.4
	1990-1999	56	21.9
	≥ 2000	87	34.0
Motivation to migrate	To rejoin or follow the family	62	24.2
	Work	89	34.8
	To join husband / marriage	36	14.1
	Education	52	20.3
	To be placed in the care of a parent or relative in Dakar	17	6.6
Number of days spent in the village	None	67	26.2
	≤ 1 week	40	15.6
	≤ 2 weeks	31	12.1
	≤ 1 month	52	20.3
	≥ 1 month	66	25.8
Total		256	100.0

Table 2. Characteristics of migrants settled in Dakar
Source: Adapted from Duboz et al., 2011

Regional and local-level environmental characteristics

Senegal River valley

The period of drought that occurred in Senegal in the 1970s mostly affected the northern regions crossed by the Senegal River. In the Senegal River basin, the direct consequences of the drought were the reduction of groundnut crops and the sudden loss of cultivatable land due to wind erosion. More widely at the national level, according to the PANAUDIT advisory body, since the mid-1980s the quantity of cultivated surfaces has diminished progressively by a total of 4% (1996: 20). The primary solution to land degradation has been an increase in the area of cultivated land (Gueye et al., 2015); however, the choice to cultivate cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*) and manioc due to their short vegetative cycles and greater resistance to drought conditions has not prevented the rural exodus to urban areas. While still today the capital Dakar remains the main destination for internal movements, the decentralization policies implemented by the government in 1996 and the changes in the national economic structure have promoted the growth of several towns and secondary cities, such as Touba, M'bour, Ourossogui, Louga, Kébémér or Richard Toll, which are patent examples of urban centres that have developed in response to drought cycles and the need to take advantage of new possibilities (Gueye et al., 2015).

The Senegal River delta: Gandiol and the Langue de Barbarie

Gandiol is a geographical area located on the left bank of the Senegal River delta, a few kilometres from where it flows into the Atlantic Ocean and 10 km south of the city of Saint-Louis. Like the rest of the country, the area is subject to the alternation of two seasons. In the northern part of Senegal, rainfall rarely exceeds 350 mm per year and under the effect of climatic upheavals, a decrease has been observed in this rainfall. The year 2003 marked a turning point in Gandiol; that year was marked by copious rainfalls in the Senegal River basin which caused a significant flood. On the night of 4 October 2003, a breach was opened on the Langue de Barbarie as an emergency measure to safeguard the security of the population of Saint-Louis from the recurring flooding. The authorities decided to dig a canal downstream from the city in order to allow the waters of the river to flow into the sea; since this date, the breach has widened considerably owing to the effect of coastal currents. As recorded by the qualitative evidence collected by Sall et al., "the opening of the breach is very often considered as the factor that has accelerated the disruption of local economic life. By affecting activities based on fishing and market gardening, the opening of the breach has amplified the effects already observed and linked to climate change" (2011: 18).³

In the district of Gandiol, the gradual encroachment of the sea, together with the opening of the breach and the rising sea level are having environmental and social consequences. Not only have several forests of mangroves, which are breeding grounds for numerous species of fish, been disrupted, but also almost 20 rural villages located along the coast in the southern part of the Langue de Barbarie have been swallowed up by the waters (Communauté Rurale de Gandiol, 2010). The encroachment of the ocean has become the main source for concern in Gandiol. Its direct consequences, such as an increase in flooding, the salinization of the soil and water table, and increased sea temperatures are leading to a severe reduction in the agricultural production and a decline in fish populations and biodiversity. It is in this context, further aggravated by the drop in rainfall, that increasing numbers of the local dwellers of Saint-Louis, many of whom are fishermen, have been forced to fish further out to sea or to move to other fishing zones in the country, like Kayar, Joal, Lompoul, M'bour and Casamance (Zickgraf, 2018).

In fact, in the last quarter of the twentieth century, the movement of people from the Senegal River basin to Saint-Louis was an adaptive response to drought conditions and the difficulties of extracting water. However,

³ Authors' translation.

after the end of a dry period, newly settled areas of the city which had previously been prone to floods were inundated once again. In this regard, the flooding of Guet Ndar, the fishermen's district in Saint-Louis, which according to regional statistics is one of the most densely populated city districts in West Africa, with more than 25,000 inhabitants living in an area of 1.0 by 0.3 km (CLUVA, 2013), was a real natural disaster. The reduction of the living space available to the local population (most of the private and public buildings were destroyed by the waves), induced the Senegalese government to relocate entire communities to the locality of Khar Yalla (Tacoli, 2011).

The region of Matam

The middle course of the Senegal River crosses the historical semi-desert region of Fouta-Toro (currently the department of Podor and region of Matam). The territory of Matam, the country's largest region, with its vast plain cut through by valleys, is being shaped by a continued decline in rainfall and desert encroachment. Similarly, to other Senegalese regions, the droughts of the 1970s had a negative effect on the environmental conditions. It is in response to these intertwined processes that Guinea, Senegal, Mali and Mauritania established the Organization for the Development of the Senegal River (OMVS)⁴ which has completed two main projects: the construction of the Diama Dam designed to prevent salt water coming from the estuary of the river and the creation of the Manantali Dam to provide a reservoir during the rainy season to ensure the navigability of the river, to irrigate farmland in the dry season and to generate electricity for Dakar, Bamako and Nouakchott. However, it has only created a limited amount of additional farmland and only began to produce electricity in 2001. In 1989, this cooperation between countries bordering the Senegal River led to a conflict between Senegal and Mauritania, triggering flows of forcibly displaced persons across the river. Many years later, several refugees hosted in Senegal got visas for western and northern European countries, the USA and Australia. While the Manantali Dam has brought (limited) benefits at the national level, the artificial flooding caused by the periodical filling of the retention basin, together with the variability in the rainfall and the historically recurrent droughts, has resulted in economic damage for the still traditional agricultural sector. In particular, it has affected the cultivation of sorghum and cowpea, the most popular crops because they are cultivated on the most coveted lands with silty/loamy soil (Sall et al., 2011). As noted by Fall et al. (2010: 45), "Like any peripheral region, the Mid-Valley appears to be the victim of the national development plan which has always favoured the Atlantic facade at the expense of the periphery" (also Grechi and Agustoni, 2019).

The drastic reduction in agricultural production, coupled with a lack of adequate water extraction means, has helped to make Matam one of the main regions of origin of Senegalese international migration, mostly led by the Haalpulaar farmers, the main ethno-linguistic group of the region (representing about 88% of the local population), and the Soninke, as well as a small but well-established colony of Wolof people employed in trade and service activities. It is no coincidence that migration from the Senegal Valley, which is mainly international, dates back to the 1970s and is historically tied to the first Senegalese workers that arrived in France soon after World War I, the so-called *tirailleurs sénégalais*, following the suspension of immigration of the seamen employed in the home ports of Europe (Diarra, 1968; Bertoncetto and Bredeloup, 2004). The severe drought of the 1970s also prompted the first waves of internal migration to the large urban centres, especially Dakar and Diourbel.

⁴ Organisation pour la mise en valeur du fleuve Sénégal.

The Groundnut Basin

The Groundnut Basin (which includes the regions of Diourbel, Louga, Kaolack and Kaffrine) covers most of the Sine Saloum. In this area, subsistence agriculture, which is the main economic activity and key source of income for 57% of the rural Senegalese (World Bank, 2010), is fully dependent on rain. In fact, only 4% of the agricultural land is irrigated (Diagne-Gueye, 2008). In other words, as argued by Pélissier (1980: 34), Senegalese agriculture is highly dependent “on rainfall, its duration, its distribution, its abundance or its deficit”.⁵

The Groundnut Basin area has a Sudano-Sahelian climate which features a great variability in rainfall. In particular, the rainfall trend between 1960 and 1998 indicates that recent rainfall levels amount to less than 60% of the level estimated at the beginning of the period. Far from being gradual, this development seems to be the result of sudden changes occurring in the early 1970s (the local droughts of 1968, 1970, 1972 and 1973). The water sources consist of groundwater tables located in the lowlands, which are used to provide water to the livestock during parts of the year. Thus, the environmental water potential is mainly limited to groundwater captured through boreholes. Nonetheless, like most of the interior regions of northern Senegal, the groundnut area is affected by the Harmattan, the hot, dry wind that produces marked changes in the daily temperature. Hampering the frequency of precipitation, the Harmattan is an important factor in the loss of water resources through evapotranspiration, making it difficult to cultivate crops.

The decreasing rainfall trend, the continuous rise in temperatures associated with other environmental changes and the excessive land use for groundnut production play a particularly important role in accelerating the degradation of vegetation, worsening food security and undermining the livelihoods of communities. Until the mid-1970s, the agricultural regions of Louga and Diourbel were considered, along with the Kaolack region, destinations for *navétanes* and international migrants (Guineans, Malians and Gambians) and, to a lesser extent, as the point of departure to Ivory Coast and Gabon. However, the groundnut growing crisis has reversed the migratory dynamic of these rural regions.

The interaction of anthropogenic and climatic events has exacerbated pre-existing vulnerabilities, resulting in a massive rural exodus as the main coping mechanism. The region of Fatick was mostly affected by the drought of 1983–1984. This episode pushed thousands of farmers to migrate to the southern lands of Fouladou (the region of Kolda), and in particular to the Pata forest. They were the so-called “migrants de l’arachide”⁶ (Sidibé, 2005) who benefited from the larger “new lands”, particularly suitable for groundnut cultivation, of southern and eastern Senegal (respectively the regions of Casamance and Tambacounda).

Nowadays, with the crisis of the Groundnut Basin, young adults from these areas leave to migrate to urban areas, such as Dakar, or abroad, in the hope of finding better living conditions. These days, the destination is not so much France, but new countries, such as Spain and Italy.

2.2 Demographic situation

Like most countries in sub-Saharan Africa, Senegal is experiencing a demographic transition that is the result of a notable decline in mortality and a much slower decline in fertility. This transition is causing a considerable population growth, with slow changes in the age structure favouring an increase in the number of young people. If we consider people under the age of 15, the average is 43% for countries in West Africa. If we add to this proportion the 19% aged 15 to 24, the population under the age of 25 represents 60% of the population in the countries of sub-Saharan Africa. In other words, 6 out of 10 people are young people. This same demographic situation in Senegal explains the presence of a large number of potential internal and

⁵ Authors’ translation.

⁶ Groundnut migrants.

international migrants, since the propensity to migrate is especially high for younger adults. It seems that young adults are very mobile even if they have not finished school or university, or if they work in the informal sector.

Senegal reached a total population of 16.3 million in 2019, with a 42.8% share under the age of 15 and 19.6% for the 15 to 24 age group, the one with the highest propensity towards internal and international migration. In 2020, total fertility was estimated at 4.5 live births per woman, down from a high of above 7 in the 1960s, 1970s and until 1985. The increase in life expectancy at birth, with a hiatus in the 1990s, has led to an estimated value of 66.0 years for men and 70.2 for women in 2020. In 2020, the infant mortality rate and the under-five mortality rates were estimated at 29.5 and 40.0 per thousand, respectively. All data refer to the World Population Prospects 2019 projections (UNDESA, 2019a).

Considering the population above the age of 25, the human capital indicators show that more than half of the population has no education, 19% completed primary education and only 5% have a post-secondary education. The mean length of schooling is estimated at 4.3 years (European Commission, Joint Research Centre, 2018).

Figure 6. Population prospects for Senegal 1950-2100.
Source: UNDESA, 2019a.

Future population growth in Senegal (UNDESA, 2019a) is rooted in the present population structure and the present patterns of population change. The expected increase in the Senegalese population (figure 6) represents a considerable potential increase in the number of emigrants in the coming decades. It seems that the country's demographic dividend has not been captured. However, it could be captured with sufficient investments in social sectors (education and health). This would lead to economic growth and consequently a lower interest in international migration. When considering the detailed human capital projections (European Commission, Joint Research Centre, 2018), the general population growth will lead to potentially very different scenarios depending on the investments in educational attainment and, hence, to very different pathways in socio-economic development and the ensuing emigration from Senegal.

2.3 Socio-cultural context

Socio-cultural roots of mobility

As far as the social and cultural representations associated with internal and international migration are concerned, it is very relevant to take into account the national and sub-regional socio-cultural context when addressing the issue of the desire to migrate. From an eco-geographical point of view Senegal belongs to the Sahel, which remains fundamentally both an area of agro-climatic constraints and a place in which the economy was and still is based on agro-pastoral activities. Under these conditions, mobility developed into

and prevailed as an adjustment strategy. It is therefore historically an essential component in the resilience of Sahelian societies vis-à-vis climatic adversity and the 'vagaries' of life. For De Bruijn and Van Dijk (2003), mobility is the most important strategy of adaptation and survival of the Sahelian populations in the face of climatic adversity.

It is reported that the Toucouleur marabouts who Islamized the historical Sudanese area had spread the following message, exultant towards travel, to the inhabitants of the valley of the Senegal River: "*Oh, people of Fouta, migrate if you know the bliss*" (Sall, 2011).

It therefore legitimized leaving, and indeed it was seen to be the most frequently chosen answer. In the river valley, an adage expresses the both salutary and obligatory nature of leaving at a crucial moment: "so yadu yonti, djondé ko ayiba", which can be translated as: "If it is time to leave, staying is a vice". In other words, for millions of Africans "being mobile" is not an exception but rather a "way of life" (De Bruijn, 2007: 110). "Mobility is engrained in the history, daily life and experiences of the population" (de Bruijn et al., 2001: 1). Narrowing down the attention to the Senegalese context, far from being an exception to sedentariness, migration instead emerges as an ongoing phase in which mobility and sedentariness are a concrete "outcome of a relation" (Adey, 2010). Historically shared ideas, socio-cultural practices, behaviours and artefacts help to reinforce a "culture of migration" (degli Uberti and Riccio, 2017) and the collective perception and acknowledgement of migration and migrants as most desirable option to improve living conditions.

The droughts of the 1970s accentuated this tendency towards migration, which grew stronger over the following decades due to the difficulties arising from the contradictory, sometimes perverse, effects of World Bank structural adjustment policies and devaluation. The investments made by the emigrants in their land of origin ended up making the migrant a success model whose trajectory people sought to follow. The study of Kane (2001), among many others, has examined how certain social events, such as celebrations of local cultural customs, become an opportunity for communities to show their gratitude to migrants who had invested in the local development of their territories.

The image of the migrant is one of financial and material well-being. As noted by Hamidou Dia (2007) in the following account: "*The advent of money as the primary medium of exchange is consecrated by the emergence of new 'figures of success'. These are figures of change inasmuch as they relegate to the background the old figures of legitimation that conferred a certain status in the public space. Among the new figures, it is first and foremost the figure of the migrant. Even if the valley is not their place of anchorage, the Modu-modu (Ndiaye, 1998), namely the Wolof and Murid migrant, has become a model of economic and social success in Senegal. This change has not been without consequences*" (Dia, 2007).⁷

Made into a true social cult, the act of migrating appeals to young people in rural areas as well as to those in urban areas who face the difficulties of entering a labour market with a shortage of demand. The social cult is also reinforced by the ostentatious behaviour of returning migrants and the media that help to forge an image of Europe as a land of plenty (Sall, 2011; degli Uberti and Riccio, 2017), giving even more force to the Wolof adage that affirms that "*Ku dul tuki, dou kham fou deukh nékhé*", in other words, he who does not travel will not know where it is good to live.

Social networks

Any migratory move, whether internal or international, is inseparable from the family, village (or social in general) and religious context. We can distinguish informal networks from formal networks. As noted by Hily, Berthomière and Mihaylova (2004), informal networks do not need to be set up and they are generally based on ties of kinship and/or belonging to the same territory (village) or religion. The analysis of migration

⁷ Authors' translation.

networks allows us to show how they fit into the transnational context that Dia evokes through the expression: “villages multi-situés du Fouta Toro en France”.⁸ Kane (2001) analyses this phenomenon by looking at the case of Thilogne Association Développement (TAD)⁹, an association with geographical branches located in Dakar, France, Italy, Gabon and the United States. The main aim of the association is to help recent Senegalese migrants to integrate and adapt to the host societies.

It is necessary to bear in mind the constraining nature of the hold that these networks sometimes have over their members. Being part of the community network becomes the norm.

“If [the person] is working and has no serious concerns, the delegation issues a warning. If the person keeps refusing, they are banned from the fund, i.e., they can no longer count on the group’s solidarity in the event of difficulties (e.g., accident, illness, death, etc.). In addition, when they go to the village, a letter follows or precedes them to be read in public. It follows that when an event takes place in the family of the violator of the fund regulations, the villagers are ordered to shun ceremonies (baptism, marriage, etc.): in the economy of the regulations structuring life in the village, to boycott an important event is a supreme affront”¹⁰ (Dia, 2008)

“In fact, once they arrive at the places of destination, the children of migrants originally from our village of reference, but born and socialized to a large extent in Dakar, take up the classic pattern of the routes used by immigrants of the Senegal River valley to settle in the migratory territories: accommodation through networks of relatives, integration into the institutions of socialization established in the place of arrival. This is how they join the village association which offers hospitality and mitigates the effect of social exteriority in a very different racial, continental, residential and economic context.”¹¹ (Dia, 2008)

The notion of networks is well documented in the literature on international migration. These studies take an approach which focuses either on the organizational methods of migrants and the formal or informal circles they create in the host countries, or on the informal channels set up in the countries of departure (and transit) to organize both regular and irregular departures (Hily, Berthomière and Mihaylova, 2004).

The factors around which these networks are formed and revolve are diverse: nationality, the region of origin (the hometown, village, neighbourhood, etc.), ethnicity or religion. However, nationality seems to be one of the most frequent references in the establishment of networks of migrants in host countries. These networks, which give rise to forms of social legitimacy, are set up to facilitate the improvement of the socio-professional, security and legal conditions of Senegalese nationals abroad regardless of the host country (Kanté, 2020). These relational networks can also link people owing to their area of origin. In this case, they identify themselves with their village, or the district or municipality to which they provide social investments. So, “grouped together abroad in village development associations (AVD), migrants engage in the social development of their native lands by financing basic infrastructure such as dispensaries, maternity wards, schools and boreholes, thus taking the place of a state incapable of ensuring its traditional mission of public service”¹² (Sall, 2008: 211). For

⁸ “Multi-located villages of Fouta Toro in France”.

⁹ Thilogne is a village in the Matam region, located 55 km away from Matam.

¹⁰ Authors’ translation.

¹¹ Authors’ translation.

¹² Authors’ translation.

instance, the migrants from the Senegal River valley have played a major role in the development of the social infrastructure in this part of Senegal.

Religious networks, which in the case of Senegal take the form of brotherhoods, are very dynamic both in organizing departures and promoting their members in a socio-professional light once abroad. So, "brotherhood networks are particularly dynamic in organizing new migrant departures. The end of labour migration led, as early as 1974, to unprecedented dynamism among unofficial support networks for departing candidates exploring new destinations which offered easy entry and real possibilities of integration and enrichment"¹³ (Tall, 2008: 155).

We can also ponder migration from the perspective of distancing oneself from family and social networks in general and therefore dismissing social ties. Indeed, leaving one's land and family area may reflect a desire to be free from obligations in order to be able to realize oneself. This represents the internalization of the fact that self-realization necessarily involves taking a distance, at some point in life, from what is most valuable to the person: the family. As clearly emphasized by Mbodji (2008): "Experienced as an obstacle to self-actualization, the group offers individuals only one alternative: to move away from it. The motivations of young people, beyond economic imperatives, also seem to be linked to a pressing need to grow as an individual. This need is accompanied by the feeling that self-realization can only be achieved far from one's own. A temporary remoteness to escape daily obligations and strong and multiple social pressures"¹⁴ (Mbodji, 2008: 314).

Education

The relationship between education and migration can be framed in several terms. Drawing from different contributions, Williams (2009) distinguishes three perspectives: the first postulates an effect of education on the propensity to migrate. In this case, the higher the level of education, the greater the propensity to migrate. This can be understood insofar as more education and, therefore, human capital is deemed synonymous with more opportunities, including in the field of migration. The second perspective establishes a very negative relationship between education and certain aspects of migration. The last perspective argues that education has no effect on the propensity to migrate.

In areas of emigration such as the Senegal River valley, the links between education and migration appear more complex, mediated or influenced by factors such as gender (Chort et al., 2017; Chort and Senneré, 2018) and social status or environment (Van der Land and Hummel, 2013).

Since the men are the ones who traditionally migrate, migration is a selective process in northern Senegal. The migration of women occurs above all in the context of family reunification: it is, for example, the case of almost all women who left for France during the 1980s and 1990s to join their husbands. This trend is still valid today and, in some cases, might lead girls who are going to get married to drop out of school. Based on ethnographic research on young girls who were in schooling, Newman (2019; 2020) describes how for many of them the decision to join the husband who had previously emigrated is a deliberate choice.

Furthermore, in the Senegal River valley it seems that social structuring shapes the relationship between education and migration in a particular way. Indeed, a clear example is the Haalpulaar society that is organized in castes, with the noble castes at the top, followed by free men, artisans and finally the servile castes. For Auriola and Demonsant (2012), in villages, for parents of non-ruling families who do not own enough land to cover their basic needs, sending their children to school would be a way of giving them a greater chance to migrate later, because of the positive relationship between state education and migration. However, among the ruling families, often belonging to the noble caste, a religious education is privileged in the run-up to the planned migration.

¹³ Authors' translation.

¹⁴ Authors' translation.

It is important to put this risk in perspective and consider that often the choice is the result of a collective decision (Sall, 2011). Especially those individuals envisioning (irregular) migration evaluate the dangers to which they may be exposed as part of the endeavour in the light of their living conditions in Senegal.

Picture: E Diop/Unsplash.com

Risks and challenges

Migration today is inextricable from the concept of risk. Current migratory movements always involve a certain degree of uncertainty. The migratory trajectories and especially the sea and land routes “chosen” by irregular migrants entail a high degree of risk. However, it is important to put this risk in perspective and consider that often the choice is the result of a collective decision (Sall, 2011). Especially those individuals envisioning (irregular) migration evaluate the dangers to which they may be exposed as part of the endeavour in the light of their living conditions in Senegal. In most cases, their living conditions seem to justify the risks taken to escape their daily lives. This risk is also collectively assumed insofar as the members of the family or the social group of reference endorse the migratory project, however risky, insofar as they often contribute to its realization by investing money in the journey while hoping for a return on their investment.

Smuggling and the human trafficking activities that are associated with irregular migration obstruct the act of migrating and make it even more perilous (Douki and Karray, 2018). There are several types of challenge concerning international migration. The first is certainly related to the need to deconstruct the attitudes and social representations of young people who perceive international migration as the only way out. It always seems more pressing to open them up to other opportunities in the economic and social realm at the local level. The second issue concerns the positive link that should be promoted between migration and local development by rethinking how the migrants’ experience could be put to the service of the local community and how the presence of members of the local community abroad may play a positive role in promoting local development (e.g., using financial and technological transfers). Although return migration always features more circular trajectories, the second challenge should be also fostered in parallel to the creation of more favourable conditions for the more stable return of those who had left while also encouraging potential migrants to remain in place.

Economic context (national and regional profiles)

Senegal is a young republic, which gained independence from France in 1960. The country’s transition and adjustment to the post-independence period was economically challenging, with the real GDP adjusted for purchasing power parity falling by 20% between 1960 and 1970 (World Bank, 2019). To add to its economic woes, the 1970s were marked by a period of drought leading to a decline in crop production and agricultural production in general.

In 1980, the economic situation became so alarming that Senegal was among the first countries in the world to enter a World Bank-sponsored structural adjustment programme. This programme aimed to lower inflation and reduce public expenditure while ensuring the strict management of domestic demand in exchange for loans. These restrictions, combined with a large variety of structural reforms which aimed to liberalize the economy by fostering the development of a strong private sector while reducing the size of the public sector, had severe social and economic consequences on Senegalese households. Despite these efforts, inflation remained high and Senegal as well as other countries in the CFA (*Communauté financière africaine*)¹⁵ zone experienced the devaluation of the CFA franc. This led to a second series of reforms, with the privatization of public companies. At the end of the 1990s, the economic environment improved, with a sustained period of economic growth averaging 5% until the financial crisis in 2008. In 1990, Senegal’s per capita GDP amounted to 1,476 US dollars (€ 1,210) when adjusted for purchasing power parity. By 2019, this number had more than doubled, reaching 3,535 US dollars (€ 2,900). The nominal GDP also quadrupled in the last two decades. In detail, the country’s GDP amounted to 5.92 billion US dollars (€ 4.86 bn) in 2000, but reached 24.13 billion US dollars (€ 19.82 bn) in 2018 (World Bank, 2019).

The population of Senegal also tripled between 1980 and 2020. From 5.6 million in 1980, the population had reached about 15.9 million in 2018 (World Bank, 2020). This rapid growth of the population coincides with a

¹⁵ Financial Community of Africa.

period of droughts which had gone on since the mid-1970s, which particularly affected the northern part of the country, especially the Senegal River valley. This contributed to a polarized urbanization process. Indeed, the main economic and urban centres are unequally distributed. While the main urban centres of Dakar, Thiès, Ziguinchor and Saint-Louis are located on the west coast, the eastern regions are predominantly rural and dependent on subsistence farming. The consequence of these combined factors is an increased vulnerability in rural areas. The latest Senegalese Household Survey (ESAM II) reveals that 58% of households in rural Senegal live below the national poverty line while this proportion drops to 34% in the capital city of Dakar and 43% in other urban centres. Senegal has therefore been subject to a rural exodus to the main urban centres and especially towards Dakar, with the first wave of Senegalese emigrants coming from remote rural areas such as the Senegal River valley.

As already mentioned, the internal movements are mostly tied to the historical patterns of seasonal migration from rural to urban areas or between urban centres during the dry season (noorane and navétanes), mainly taking place and increasing within the framework of the agro-pastoral cycle. It mostly concerns young unmarried men who work in the city during the dry season and return during the growing season to participate in agricultural activities. These rural-urban-rural movements are a clear exemplification of the circular flows of the younger generations who do not emigrate permanently from their area of origin (Ba et al., 2017: 20). Commuting practices from rural to urban or urban to urban areas rather than one-way migration to the main urban centres of the country are a characteristic that has shaped most of the recent internal migration in Senegal.

As mentioned earlier, severe drought in the early 1970s made rain-fed cultivation prone to risks in a region of Senegal where families rely on subsistence farming. In general, migrating and earning remittances became a solution to minimize the risk of food insecurity. This is also highlighted in Kabandji (2013), with one of the interviewees stating that *"[o]nly two interventions prevented the residents of the (Senegal River) valley from being wiped off the map of Senegal [...]: the intervention of the migrants and the intervention of USE (Union Solidarité Entraide), who enabled the people in the valley to survive after years of drought. They helped people survive, they invested in the social arena and they contributed to investment in pure development to set up mechanisms that could be productive and grow"* (interview by Kabandji, 2013, USE, Dakar, 2009). The first departures to other Senegalese cities were mainly people of low social classes and castes. Migration became a long journey of people trying their luck in different countries and regions (West Africa, Europe) and taking advantage of every single opportunity. For instance, some migrants would first hold odd jobs in Dakar before leaving for Abidjan (Ivory Coast). From there they could work as waiters on ships or move to Sierra Leone, South Africa or Congo where they could become diamond dealers (see Sall, 2010 and Kabandji, 2013).

More recently, in 2014, Senegal adopted the medium- to long-term development "Plan Senegal Émergent" (PSE). This plan serves as a strategy and the reference for the economic and social policy looking towards 2035. This new plan has three areas of priority:

- 1) To foster a structural transformation of the economy through, among others, improving the business climate, automating administrative procedures and simplifying tax and legal procedures;
- 2) To promote human capital by improving living conditions and reducing social inequalities;
- 3) To promote good governance, which creates social peace by reinforcing security and protects rights and rule of law.

In 2018, the GDP growth was about 6.4%. Within the framework of the PSE, Senegal has also contracted debt to allow for major investments in infrastructure (for example, motorways and the new town of Diamniadio). The COVID-19 pandemic significantly affected the country with a drop in the real GDP from an estimated 6.4 in the pre-pandemic period, which was predicted to fall to a level of 2.8 in 2021, as projected according to a baseline COVID-19 scenario (source: African Development Bank, 2020). At the same time, and because

the Senegalese diaspora reside in countries where the pandemic had major consequences on the economy (France, Italy, Spain, USA, etc.), the inflow of remittances was also negatively affected by the pandemic.

As an indication of the recent economic struggles, the IOM's Missing Migrants Project recorded 500 deaths (IOM, 2020), most of which during the months of October and November 2020, of migrants departing from the West African coast, particularly from Senegal. As we can observe in Pictures 1 and 2 below, the pirogues and their helmsmen often come from the fishing sector and the logic is that they would rather risk their lives trying to reach Spain than compete with fishing trawlers from the European Union, China and Russia (see also degli Uberti, 2014).¹⁶ The fisheries partnership agreement concluded between the EU and Senegal is considered by many to be part of the problem as it strips Senegalese artisanal fishermen of their main resource. By way of a reminder, this partnership was signed between Senegal and the EU to allow EU vessels from France and Spain to fish in Senegalese waters for a yearly financial compensation of € 1.7 million between 20 November 2014 and 19 November 2019. The EU and Senegal went on to renew this partnership for the following five years (i.e., between 18 November 2019 to 17 November 2024) (European Commission, 2020).

Picture 1. Migrants and pirogues in Fimela.

Source: <https://www.seneweb.com>

Picture 2. The group arrested in Rufisque.

Source: <https://www.seneweb.com>

¹⁶ The term "pirogue" does not refer to a specific kind of boat but identifies the wooden fishing boats traditionally used by West African fishermen.

2.4 Political context

Senegal is one of the most stable democracies in Africa, with successive presidential transitions since gaining independence in 1960. It is one of the few African countries that has not had military coup d'états and that has successfully handed down presidential power since its independence. Senegal was a focal point in French West Africa as the cities of Saint-Louis (1763-1902) and Dakar (1902-1960) were successively the capitals of the French colonies of West Africa until independence in 1960. Because of its position in the French West African colonies and its relative stability, Senegal was a destination country for migrants until the mid-1970s.

Geopolitical dynamics, political cleavages

The first president of the newly independent republic of Senegal was Léopold Sédar Senghor, leader of the UPS (Union Progressiste Sénégalaise). The Senghor presidency was a one-party rule. The Senghor regime banned all political parties in 1964, with the exception of the African Reunion Party. The first real opposition party to be recognized legally was the Senegalese Democratic Party whose leader, Abdoulaye Wade, was sent to jail for criticizing the Senghor regime. Senghor decided to retire in 1980, transferring the presidency to Abdou Diouf. Diouf, a civil servant by training, contributed to the consolidation of the democracy in Senegal. A first major act in this regard was that he authorized and legally recognized seven political parties, which were mainly part of the opposition. It was also under Abdou Diouf that several private and independent radio and television channels were given licences to operate, reinforcing the freedom of the press and the right to criticize the ruling government.

Despite adopting a multi-party system, Diouf was re-elected three times, in 1983, 1988 and 1993. However, his last two victories were contested and there were allegations of electoral fraud. The first democratic transition took place in 2000 with the leader of the PDS, Abdoulaye Wade, beating Abdou Diouf. There were allegations and turmoil about the real winner of the elections, and in order to quell potential conflicts or turmoil, Abdou Diouf called Abdoulaye Wade to congratulate him even before the official results of the election. The 2012 presidential election further consolidated the Senegalese democratic system with the election of Macky Sall, who became the fourth president of Senegal.

Conflicts and security issues

Senegal has experienced only relatively minor civil unrest and armed conflict since gaining independence in 1960. The only threat to the political stability is the separatist movement in Casamance, the Movement of the Democratic Forces of Casamance (MFDC), which claims the independence of the Casamance region from Senegal. More recently, neighbouring countries such as Mali have been under the growing influence of Islamist groups, posing an overall threat to the stability of the Sahel region. Despite these potential risks, at present Senegal is relatively safe against these Islamist groups, which is partly due to a strong practice of Sufi Islam organized around a small number of brotherhoods, among which the *Muridiyya* and *Tijaniyya*.

Violation of human rights

Senegal's march toward democracy is very impressive but the country still needs to improve in aspects of human rights. For instance, the country's prisons are overcrowded and the rights of prisoners to decent living conditions have not been a priority so far. There are also issues concerning the independence of the justice system as the sitting president and his minister of justice appoints state attorneys and judges, which undermines their independence. This has been a source of controversy in Senegal as there is the impression that the government and political allies of the ruling president were shielded from prosecution when the Inspection Générale d'État (IGE, the state body which investigates all government bodies or public servants handling public funds) discovered irregularities and attempts to embezzle public funds. Meanwhile, leaders of the opposition have been to prison for minor offences such as insulting the president (e.g., Guy Marius Sagna) or when accused of public funds mismanagement (e.g., Karim Wade, son of the former president Abdoulaye

Wade, and Khalifa Ababacar Sall, one the former leaders of the Socialist party). Additionally, there are still persistent issues concerning discrimination based on sexual orientation.

Migration policies on internal mobility and international mobility to the EU

Senegal used to be a country of immigration before becoming a country with a large diaspora mainly residing in other African countries, Europe and the USA. The changes in migration patterns and trends, with the rise of irregular migration to Europe, have forced the government to adopt more proactive migration policies. Nonetheless, changes in the approach to migration policy have also been pushed by the need to support and meet the needs of the growing number of Senegalese abroad and returning migrants.

On the one hand, the Senegalese government increasingly acknowledges migrants' contribution to the Senegalese economy and to the development efforts. Migrants play an active part in improving the livelihoods of their families through remittances (Diagne and Rakotonarivo, 2010). According to the World Bank, international financial remittance to low- and middle-income countries reached 466 billion US dollars in 2017 of which 38 billion were sent to sub-Saharan African countries (World Bank, 2016). This is more than double the amount of official aid to sub-Saharan Africa (World Bank, 2019, see also figure 7). The growing importance of these international financial flows has forced the government to consider the diaspora as an integral part of Senegal. As a gesture, the Senegalese diaspora was allocated about 15 representatives in the Senegalese parliament in 2017. Consequently, there has been a paradigm shift in migration policy from a labour export perspective to a diaspora policy focus. Migrants are therefore encouraged to return as entrepreneurs to boost the local economy (Sinatti, 2009). This has prompted the creation of the *Fonds d'Appui à l'Investissement des Sénégalais de l'Extérieur* (FAISE), which aims to support Senegalese migrants who have concrete projects but lack sufficient funds to start their business.

Figure 7. World Bank data on remittances in US dollars.

Source: World Bank, 2016.³⁷

³⁷ Calculation based on data from the IMF Balance of Payments Statistics database and data releases from central banks, national statistical agencies and World Bank country desks. NB: The remittance amounts are underestimated, as unofficial channels are still predominant.

There is a section of the Senegalese National Police force whose goal is to stop undocumented migrants from taking pirogues towards Spain (see pictures 1 and 2 above). More recently, two major arrests were made during the month of September 2020. The first arrest is credited to the Fimela police who arrested 73 Senegalese migrants, including seven women and a two-year-old child, who were heading to Spain (source: Senegalese national police communication department). A second batch of arrests took place on 22 September, in which the national police "Section de recherches" (SR) arrested 14 young Senegalese who were about to embark for Spain as well. They were living in a house in construction in Rufisque, on the outskirts of Dakar.

Besides the efforts of the Senegalese national police to stop undocumented outflows, Senegal's migration policy includes a partnership between Senegal and European destination countries with the aim to promote legal migration and reduce undocumented migration. In this regard and given that a significant proportion of the migrants reaching the Spanish coast are Senegalese (26,000 migrants who entered Spain in 2006 originate from Senegal), in 2006 Spain and Senegal initiated a recruitment programme. The Spanish Foreign Ministry announced the implementation of a recruitment office in Dakar in order to contract locally Senegalese wishing to work in Spain. In exchange for their effort to control undocumented migration, the Senegalese government received 15 million euros from Spain over a period of five years.

Profile of selected urban areas: the Dakar region

The empirical part of the qualitative field research was conducted in the urban and peri-urban area composing the so-called Dakar region, the capital of Senegal.

Today the majority of the Senegalese population live in the urban areas of Senegal. Since 1960, when 700,000 people lived in urban areas (23% of its national population at the time of independence), the urban population increased to 8.3 million in 2020 (50%) (Dietz *et al.*, 2020). Today Dakar has become a huge metropolis that hosts most of the urban population of Senegal. At the same time, the other major cities have also gradually expanded: alongside Touba and Diourbel, at least six or even seven other cities have more than 100,000 inhabitants (Dietz *et al.*, 2020).

The choice of Dakar is mainly justified by the important role that the Senegalese capital plays as a crossroads for the internal and international trajectories of Senegalese migrations (Sinatti 2008). Internal migration has been increasing for ten years, particularly towards the regions of Dakar and the region of Diourbel, which are respectively the economic and religious centres of the country (Ba *et al.*, 2017: 16). The Dakar region concentrates nearly a quarter of the Senegalese urban population (23.2%) in an area corresponding to only 0.3% of the country; 820,000 migrants, accounting for 43% of internal migrants, are concentrated in the urban area of the capital (ANSD, 2014).

As already mentioned, unlike in the past, it is important to point out that today internal migration towards Dakar is mostly of urban origin; moreover, recent migrants have a higher level of education and are older than earlier migrants when they arrive in Dakar. While women migrate most often for marriage, men move more often in order to pursue their studies even if the search for more profitable job opportunities is still the main driving force. Dakar remains a central destination for internal migrants in Senegal, but the migrants' profiles have changed greatly in the last 60 years (Duboz *et al.*, 2011). The region of Dakar has a positive net migration, being a strong place of attraction for people living in the surrounding regions. As the main urban centre of Senegal, the Dakar region provides most of the services and job opportunities in the secondary and tertiary sectors. Its coastal (Zone des Niayes) and littoral zones are host to intense primary sector activities: fishing in the former, and horticulture in the latter. It is also an important regional hub for many international structures with advanced tertiary functions (Ba *et al.*, 2017: 14). No less importantly, Dakar is also the main place of investment for migrants (Sall, 2004; Tall, 1999), particularly in the real estate sector. These investments can be seen as economic incentives for potential international migrants to realize their migratory plans.

The Dakar region as a whole has had a central place in international emigration from the years 1980-1990 onwards (DPS, 1998; Robin *et al.*, 1999), with the specific neighbourhoods and the urban living experience becoming influential in the increase and diffusion of migratory behaviour. As pointed out by Ndione and Lalou (2004; 2008), especially when they are on the receiving end of the migrants' economic reinvestments, the neighbourhoods of origin often play an important role in promoting international migration, also owing to the social cohesion and strong identity and belonging among the neighbourhood population that often previously migrated from rural areas.

It is not uncommon to hear that international migration is merely an extension of internal migration. Since the 1970s, the majority of the people who have migrated internationally and transited through Dakar originated from rural and/or peripheral areas. However, "in the past 15 years, the probability of migrating abroad appears to be much higher among Dakar residents born in the city"¹⁸ (Ndione and Lalou, 2004: 256).

Faced with an acceleration of the urban crisis, some secondary cities (e.g., M'bour, Kaolak, Thiès, Ourossogui), conceived as "socio-cultural places of relations and exchanges", have become significant determinants of global migration trajectories (Ndione, 2012). In parallel, the increasing re-emergence of unauthorized boat migration to the Canary Islands, Dakar has somehow become less attractive and migrants manage to skip the city in favour of some peripheral and rural areas that offer easier access to migration abroad (e.g., Kafountine in Casamance, Kayar on the Great Coast and Saint-Louis in northern Senegal). However, Dakar remains the place where most of the emigrants develop their migratory projects.

More recently, since the early 2000s, the growing presence of Chinese investments in the capital, the arrival of African entrepreneurs and the transmission of experience from China are shaping new patterns of mobility. This prompts questions about how the motivations and reasons for the appeal of Dakar and international migration trajectories are changing.

¹⁸ Authors' translation.

Picture: Nino Jackjr/Unsplash.com

3. Results of the analysis

3.1 Who moves: profile

The traditional framework for understanding migrant decision-making is based on the push-and-pull model, that is, factors that encourage people to leave their place of origin (push), but also elements of attraction at the chosen destination (pull). Despite the merits of this model, it is necessary to go beyond this framework to elaborate a more adequate answer to a complex question: why do people choose to move?

In Senegal, among several ethnic groups, the desire to move internally or to go abroad is mostly influenced by socio-cultural and economic factors. However, when examining Senegalese migration abroad, it seems that those who are willing to move cannot or do not have the means to choose their preferred destination. The aim of the FUME project is to examine migration aspirations and trajectories while accounting for the role of cities, such as Dakar, and how the urban experience often becomes a stepping stone or an anchor that prevents further international movement. In this perspective, the research on migration intentions prompts an exploration of what shapes different migration timelines, by focusing on the migrants' experiences according to their time of arrival in Dakar. Contrary to the initial methodological plan, the collected evidence led us to categorize the migrants according to two groups only, rather than three: newcomers (arriving less than five years ago) and settlers (arriving five or more years ago).¹⁹

The majority of the interviewees come from the regions of Saint-Louis and Matam, most often from the rural villages and small towns (e.g., Ndioum, Ronkh, Kanel, Orkadiéré, Agnam Civol) along the course of the Senegal River. These areas of the middle and upper Senegal River valley, which are known for their agriculture, are also some of the territories most affected by climate change and environmental degradation. The sample also includes individuals from the regions in the Groundnut Basin, a historical area of emigration: Diourbel, Thiès, Fatick and Kaolack. Some participants in the study originated from the region of Casamance, an isolated area affected by security issues.

The majority of people we spoke to have kin or close friends who have migrated or are currently living abroad. Only a handful of the interviewees had already had a personal migration experience abroad.

Almost half of the interviewees had not received any education at all or only attended Koranic schools, while the remaining majority had only completed a primary or lower level of education (16); a few, however, had achieved a secondary level of education (4) or a post-secondary level of education (5).

¹⁹ It is worth mentioning that according to the recent research which also takes into consideration the conditions of natives in Dakar and their attitudes towards migration, the evidence suggests that migrants from rural areas integrate better than natives in the economic system of Dakar, whatever their time of arrival (Ndione and Lalou, 2004; Antoine et al., 1995). The probability of migrating internationally proves to be higher for natives of Dakar than for migrants from rural areas. Not only does the influence of imaginaries of a westernized lifestyle play an attracting role but, more importantly, lower levels of education (Salam Fall and Mboup, 1995; Bocquier, 1995) coupled with a less developed network of relationships, which make it more difficult to enter a highly unregulated labour market..

From a socio-professional point of view, the majority of the interviewees were employed in the service (e.g., drivers, carters, gardeners, guardians) or the trade sector. A significant number of interviewees worked in the field of construction (e.g., bricklayers, carpenters, painters). The remaining four were students while two interviewees were unemployed. Overall, it is worthwhile underlining that despite the differences in professional sector, informal terms (the absence of any contract) shape the employment conditions of most of the interviewees.

It can be observed that while settled migrants are both older and, in most cases, with a Koranic and not a state education, the newcomers are usually younger and relatively better educated, sometimes holding a university degree or still enrolled as students, even though education was not mentioned as the reason they moved to Dakar.

While the willingness to improve their individual livelihood and the lives of relatives back in the places of origin appears to be the motivation shared equally by all of the interviewees, against the background of a challenging and chaotic urban context, the mixed and ambivalent feelings – swinging “from shame to ambition” (SenMig11) – informing the migrants’ decision to move from rural areas to Dakar, appear to shape their different attitudes and propensity towards further mobility.

3.2 Pre-migration characteristics

The empirical field research confirms previous studies that highlight how international migration from Senegal has become highly generalized in recent decades, affecting all strata of the working-age population. A greater diversification of migration profiles is documented, varying according to socio-professional category (informal sector workers, students, farmers, etc.), origin (almost all regions are affected by emigration, one such area being the Senegal River valley, rural and city areas), duration of residence (recent arrivals in Dakar versus long-term residents), gender (both women and men), levels of education (from those with no educational qualifications to those with a higher education), place of residence (residents of working-class neighbourhoods such as Pikine versus residents of non-working class neighbourhoods) and relationships with migrants living abroad (potential migrants with and without contacts with Senegalese migrants living abroad, which is an important aspect given the importance of networks in the realization of migration plans).

Economic conditions – leaving as an unavoidable outcome?

For most of the Senegalese interviewees, the decision to migrate to Dakar was the only available option to conceive of an improvement in their living conditions. In order to meet their primary economic needs, the people who moved more recently display a similar trajectory to the long-term residents and settlers. Several interviews indicated that Dakar is still the most attractive place for people of rural origin. It is the first accessible “visa-free” destination where they can aspire to and realize tangible economic achievements, as highlighted by the following interview:

My mother was a washerwoman here in Dakar and it was me who was taking care of the house. I'm a village girl and proud of it. I left the village to come and work in Dakar like many other girls of my age. When I was in the village, I took care of my brothers and sisters and at certain at certain point my mother could no longer continue her work and she returned to the village so I in turn decided to come here to Dakar to find some decent work....I was selling things. I'd also trained as a dressmaker, so it gradually allowed me to buy fabrics and sell them. I made fabrics with my hands and I sold them too. With the little profit I had, I allowed myself to buy other fabrics and resell them. I also had a certificate.
(SenMig18)

While migration most often appears to be the only way to put an end to economic constraints, the decision to leave home takes different forms as a result of more complex dynamics where other important factors are at stake, as suggested in the above account: family obligations and the reciprocity of relational duties within domestic groups overlap. Interestingly, these factors make migration an embedded component of the continuity and reproduction of the domestic group: moving to Dakar so as to ensure the perpetuation of the shared responsibility by relieving the mother of the task of supporting the family in the village. However, the very same factors could have a different effect, instead delaying or putting on hold the decision to move. This is how SenMig24 recounts the moments that preceded the realization of his long-planned migration project to become a shoemaker living in Dakar:

From 2008, I started thinking seriously that I wanted to leave my place. My friend and I had a precise project in common. When you keep seeing your childhood friends, relatives who leave and come back, sometimes bringing real changes to your hometown, you're inevitably tempted to leave. You want to try your luck too. But at the beginning my mother was categorically opposed to my wish to leave Medina. She had made a lot of effort to finance my studies at the Franco-Arab school. It was only after her death, that same year, that I decided to leave. [...] After a few years, in 2010, I finally decided to go directly to Dakar, in search of a better life.
(SenMig24)

Nonetheless, the economic hardship is not necessarily related to subsistence, it is the outcome of more specific issues such as the shortage of means for productive farming and the lack of educational facilities. Analysis of the conditions in the regions of origin prior to moving suggests that when people take migration into consideration as a strategy to search for better opportunities, this does not necessarily imply that they are completely destitute. Indeed, most of interviewees belong to families that are landowners and they engaged in subsistence farming before moving to Dakar. However, due to the lack of financial resources, most of the interviewees underlined that they were forced to rely on rudimentary technical tools to cultivate. Thus, agriculture can rarely become a concrete alternative for young people and a productive resource enabling them to earn a livelihood for themselves and their families and to offer stable prospects for long-term projects, such as building a house or getting married.

Yes, we were having trouble getting a good harvest, there were animals that came to spoil our fields. We had a problem [that we didn't have] suitable materials because the type of agriculture we were doing was traditional agriculture. Our family have a lot of land, but for me if you don't have any materials, you can't harvest good crops and you'll cultivate at a loss.... We were having problems with seeds and fertilizers and we also had problems with materials.
(SenMig09)

The first difficulty is that, what we cultivate doesn't cover us all year round for [our food] consumption, and then there's also the lack of work tools; there's also a lack of animals to do farming such as horses and our equipment is rudimentary.
(SenMig03)

As suggested by this latter account, migration from rural areas to Dakar becomes part of a mitigation strategy when families face difficulties in farming due to a lack of tools and machinery, a lack of seeds, drought, locust attacks, etc. Since agriculture is increasingly less an option for socio-economic achievement for young men who want to get married and support their parents and families, farming activities and a commitment to work the family lands in the area of origin is seen rather as a dead-end track, a path to social death. As such, migration to Dakar becomes the only viable option. The following interviewee, originating from the Casamance region, provides a vivid insight into this socio-economic dynamic.

In Diafa Douma, the conditions were very difficult. You can't have the life you want. You don't have access to some essential things in life. We sometimes prefer to leave the village, come here to work, earn our living to then return and adjust certain needs. We can't meet our needs and those of our parents. Life there is extremely difficult. There's no transport. You have to walk long distances even to go to school. That's why we prefer to come here [Dakar] to work so that we can meet our needs and those of our parents.
(SenMig13)

Despite the challenges faced in their place of origin, many interviewees portray it in an ambivalent, not fully negative way. Moving to the capital city involves increasing food, housing and transportation costs, in addition to the expected financial remittances due to the family members left behind. Although they are fully employed, some interviewees underline the less stressful and lower cost of living they enjoyed in their places of origin.

Living conditions in Ziguinchor were better than here. Casamance is better than here. Life is too difficult in Dakar. There you could have whatever you wanted. In addition, your parents were there to support you. In Dakar, this is not the case. For me, life in Casamance is better than here.

You know, in Casamance, there is no money, but with a little money you can manage your living. Life wasn't that expensive. But all the money I had was given to me; my father gave me the most. He ran the house. My mother didn't work, she is a housewife.
(SenMig22)

Social norms and economic expectations such as getting married, owning a home and being able to take care of one's parents become connotations of identity, especially in the absence of an adequate welfare state system. Among numerous young adults, the failure to achieve these social milestones, along with ongoing unemployment, make them ashamed as they are widely perceived as unproductive members of society.

Educational and professional advancement: absence of means and facilities

Among the interviewees, especially those who had arrived recently, a widely shared factor that is mentioned as triggering mobility to Dakar is the lack of opportunities of higher education in their areas of origin. Although a primary school service is available in most rural areas, the possibility for people to pursue further education or to find a first job opportunity implies moving to the nearest town.

Alhamdulillah, today we can name a lot of people who have a profession. There are a lot of people who are qualified, but they didn't have it [the opportunity] in their village.
(SenMigo2)

In addition, the difficulties in looking for a job or pursuing a training opportunity, for example in the field of dressmaking, are still a relevant issue especially for young girls and women:

[In my homeplace] it is very difficult to learn a trade; there are practically no opportunities which allow you to learn to be a trader, compared to the city. At times, there were simple workshops on mechanic and some tailoring workshops. But there weren't any more formalized courses, like trade schools or businesses schools to provide young people a job.

It's difficult to learn a trade, especially for girls. Usually the only way to find a profession is as dressmaker. There is only one sewing centre but other than that I don't see any other jobs that girls can do.
(SenMigo8)

Environmental conditions

Drawing from the accounts of the interviewees, in most of cases the worsening of the environmental conditions in their areas of origin is not mentioned as a primary motivation for leaving but as a co-constitutive factor fostering rural outmigration. Environmental factors can be understood as events such as natural disasters, droughts, water shortages and floods that can trigger migration decisions, as they can also affect other areas of the economy such as agricultural productivity. A rural exodus becomes an option for mitigating uncertainty when income from farming is unpredictable due to issues such as rainfall decline.

For us personally, we had great difficulties. Just that there are times when the rainfall is poor. Our difficulties are not in agriculture because there are people who cultivate one or two hectares, we had not already asked our father to decrease. If he was a scientist and you sowed a hectare or two then your suffering should be able to end in a year and you will rest. He should have managed it better. Our father was not asked to put all the means at our disposal, instead, to avoid more expenses, he preferred to cultivate less space. In Medina, adults have long made us believe that we have to cultivate and eat without leaving the locality. Today we are mature, we see people who succeed by emigrating. We too are naturally tempted although we know that you can find a work as a mechanical welder, carpenter, but it's very poorly paid work. There are all kind of works in the trade like selling, fishing...out there; the only problem is that they are paid little.

(SenMig30)

According to this interviewee, the increasing decline in rainfall makes farming a risky activity. While in the village the parents of the interviewee stress the importance of farming as a prospective activity for youngsters, they are tempted to migrate because they are influenced by the stories of those migrants who have successfully managed to send remittances, get married or build a house for their parents, since they have settled in Dakar or live abroad.

3.3 Pre-departure information on destination

Migration decisions are informed by perceptions and expectations associated with the places of destination. For most of interviewees, the decision to embark on a trip to Dakar is nurtured by rumours, anecdotes or ideas about the opportunities existing in the city. The information about the capital is mostly provided by migrants originating from the same village who have already left to work or study there:

I saw friends coming and going to Dakar. You know, when you're young, the name Dakar is a curiosity for everybody. You want to go see what's going on there.

(SenMig25)

Because Dakar is our capital. Anything that cannot be found in other regions can perhaps be found in Dakar. Also, this is where you get to know many people. The economy is more developed here than elsewhere. This is why we preferred to come to Dakar.

(SenMig26)

When I was little, once I came here to Dakar. I always wished to go the capital. But I remember life was hard... but not as hard as now!! When I was in the village, I often heard people saying that it was difficult to find work [in Dakar].

Things got even more difficult especially during the COVID period as we had stopped doing anything and we are staying at home. Also, we could no longer go to houses to do laundry because people were afraid of being contaminated.

(SenMig18)

I thought about Dakar as a city where life was comfortable. When I graduated from high school, I was convinced of just one thing, that I'd go to college, because I believed that if you had finished your studies, you'd get what you wanted. But it was a big let-down. I got this idea from other students who went there before me. From their stories, I thought Dakar was a laidback city...unfortunately it was not.
(SenMig12)

Migration emerges as a complex mix of feelings and expectations that are subject to changes along the migratory path, along with a rereading of the life experience. Most of the time, these feelings are not linear but rather ambivalent, as suggested by this interviewee whose wishful expectations of finishing university and finding a job in Dakar did not match his daily reality. The next sections will address this complexity.

3.4 Migration decision-making

An individual yet socially rooted decision

Regardless of the time of arrival in the Senegalese capital, the results of the qualitative interviews suggest that it is difficult to separate these exogenous socio-cultural and economic factors from the influence of personal happenings and thinking. The interviews with several persons confirmed the role played by individual initiative in the decision to migrate:

It was a personal decision and my family had no influence whatever in that decision.
(SenMig12)

It's my own decision because of my studies. I want to pursue my studies and develop my knowledge far from home.
(SenMig28)

First, it's my own decision. It was a personal idea, and no one asked me to leave, I just saw the men from my community leaving and I wanted to do the same. [...] I have now come to Dakar to work so that my family can eat rice with fish when in the past we only lived on corn and millet. Now our way of life will begin to change.
(SenMig20)

However, this shift in Senegalese migration patterns does not preclude the importance of social as well as cultural anchors in shaping individual desire. One of the key experts offers an explanation while taking into consideration social transformations and changes occurring in the balance of intra-family relationships:

Perhaps the choice is more and more individualized because it is society that has less weight on individuals; it might be that more and more often the family or the head of the family has less and less control and also less resources to take care of them. People somehow try to find their own means. It's like the person who manages to find a job on a building site and brings back 1500 F per day; if this person finds a way, he won't wait for authorization to leave, and he says this to warn people when he has already decided. Today society has less and less hold over the individual, the family has broken up so people within the family tend to make their own decisions.
(SenExp02)

The full significance of the personal inclination to migrate emerges when it is understood as a means of social self-affirmation within the closest network of relationships. At first glance, "looking for money to get out of here" or the willingness to "discover another way of life and above all learn what is going on elsewhere" (SenMig29) or "to collect a lot of knowledge" (SenMig03) are the most common reasons given to leave the villages and head towards Dakar. Another perspective is suggested by one of the women interviewed, who explains how the longing for personal advancement and recognition is tightly bound to expectations associated with a communal repertoire of shared socio-cultural behaviours and values.

The full significance of the personal inclination to migrate emerges when it is understood as a means of social self-affirmation within the closest network of relationships.

The first time I travelled was on a Tabaski day. Because I woke up on that Tabaski day without having a sheep to slaughter or money to buy vegetables. I did everything to be able to provide a Tabaski meal for my family, but to no avail and it made me cry. This lack of means made me leave my village for Dakar.

The poorest in these countries [abroad] have better living conditions than us; for example, housekeepers are paid better abroad than in Senegal, because they know the true value of these women and have total respect for them.

(SenMig11)

The existential discomfort caused by the inability to preserve the reproduction of socio-cultural family life enhances her conviction to migrate: "I want to emigrate [abroad] because I think where I am going is better than where I come from".

Socio-cultural factors

Further explanations of how the individual choice in favour of territorial mobility is rooted in particular social expectations and values shared among individuals are provided by two men both belonging to the Peul ethnic group (also referred to as Fulani or Fulbe).²⁰

It's always been almost a tradition with us. [...] It's in our culture ... we, the men, only move in search of what is best for us and for our families, which means we always attempt the adventure somewhere else.

(SenMig24)

It is natural for us Fulani. When you begin to be aware of your very difficult family situation, it is normal to seek to help your family. And going to Dakar seemed to be the best option [...]. Since 2003, I had only one desire: to leave the place.

(SenMig30)

Similarly, a key expert emphasizes the connection between ethnicity and the propensity for internal and international migration.

...there are cultural factors, the Toucouleurs are eternal travellers, the Soninke are eternal travellers, the Man-jack people are eternal travellers, as opposed to the Serer who are sedentary, anchored to their land so they migrate little, or not far. The other factor is the economic factors from the 1990s. Before it was a labour migration because the Toucouleurs and the Soninke went to France [to work] in the factories, it was the golden period and the economy was working and workers were needed. Then, from the end of 1973, the cycles of drought began and France could no longer support the peanut growers who had gone under without any control from the Senegalese state or any subsidies (from the Senegalese state) and the doldrums set in in the Groundnut Basin.

Second wave of migration then was the Wolofs, the Murids in Touba [and] in all these areas, Louga, Diourbel. The third factor is these economic factors, with young people, the question of employment, young people and employment in urban areas. From the 2000s on, there is more and more urban migration, there is tension over employment, youth unemployment. Suddenly, there is this migratory movement from the cities which can be linked to another phenomenon, which is called, that is to say, globalization, international geopolitics, fishing issues. It [the migration movement] has become a phenomenon, since the ACP countries and the African countries signed the contract with Europe. You have Yaoundé and Lomé where these agreements are signed, there is the whole aspect of exploitation of resources through fishing which some people mention, there is a colleague who said, now as the Lebous fishermen no longer have any fish to catch, they put the people in the pirogues, so people replace the fish and so it continues.

(SenExp01)

²⁰ The Peul people, who are scattered throughout many parts of West Africa, from Lake Chad in the east to the Atlantic coast, are originally a pastoral people, whose lives and social organization are dominated by the needs of their herds.

The mobility of people, whether internal or international, is the result of historical and socially shared values, practices and beliefs. These reinforce a 'culture of migration' firmly rooted in Senegalese heritage (Sinatti, 2011; degli Uberti and Riccio, 2017) and foster a collective perception of migration as the best choice to improve living conditions as opposed to staying home, which is associated with failure or a lack of ambition. The persistence of a particular migration culture over the generations may explain why migration continues to occur even when in actual fact the context of destinations such as Dakar has changed due to a progressive and significant decline in labour demand. The same goes for international migration, where national and international political mechanisms are increasingly implemented to curb the mobility of irregular migrants.

Education, professional training and employment

Although education is generally perceived as an important social value by interviewees, it is only mentioned as a direct reason for migrating to Dakar by some long-settled migrants. Even before the 1970s, education and trade were the main triggers for internal migration from both the northern regions of Saint-Louis and Matam and the more central areas of Thiès, Diourbel and Kaolack, which are the interviewees' main regions of origin:

Education is one of the most important things in life. If you aren't educated, it's very difficult to get by even if you are working in commerce.
(SenMig16)

In our village at Agnam Civol we attach great importance to the school. Almost all the children go to school...
(SenMig15)

The great importance that several interviewees attached to schooling, vocational training or state education in general is underscored by the contrast with the Koranic upbringing often prescribed by their parents and tradition. The education-related motivations for migration fall within a social framework in which boys' daily lives in the villages are primarily divided between studying the Koran in the *daara*²¹ and engaging in agricultural activities. In contrast, domestic tasks predominate for girls in a context of a general lack of educational opportunities and other public services.

When I was in Kanel, I didn't know what to do...I couldn't do anything except to learn the Koran and to practice agriculture. [...] In the village I was a talibé [disciple] and at the same time I was farming. At one point I realized that it wasn't working. The pursuit of money and some life improvement...that's why I decided to come to Dakar to be able to get out of it.
(SenMig09)

Living conditions in the village were unbearable. [...] There were no primary schools, middle schools or high school. There was only one dispensary [health post] where doctors weighed you and just gave you paracetamol. In addition, there was no water or electricity. Down there the children don't study anything except Arabic; people only take the children to learn the Koran.
(SenMig11)

No, there was a Franco-Arab school, but I was in Koranic school most of the time, like many young people there. [...] The school there is not valued at all, Koranic education is the prevalent and domination education there.
(SenMig24)

²¹ The *daara* is the main form of rural organization of the Murid brotherhood. Like the *da'ira* in urban areas, the *daara* is the Koranic school where *talibés* (disciples) receive a religious education in addition to working in the fields.

Although there is no causal link between internal migration and the attendance of a madrasa, most of the young people who migrated to Dakar more than five years ago had very little or no schooling and were mostly employed in agriculture before leaving their place of origin. Overall, the evidence in the field does not allow us to provide any clear and straightforward explanations for the relationship between the type or level of education and the degree of propensity to emigrate, given that migration affects both secondary school students as well as Koranic students, who do not find low-skilled work abroad humiliating.

As noted by one of the key experts interviewed in the survey, this relationship remains a rather complex and open issue that calls into question the assessment of educational practices in terms of their social functionality.

For me, [this relationship] is very relative if we see the high level of achievement of the Murids, people who have never been to school. In that case [...] most of the successful migrants did not go to French school. But migration is selective; in fact, as soon as you say education we think of the French school, but education is not only the French school. Koranic education from an early age puts children to the test; they are people who know how to travel and to put themselves to the test. Intellectual education through the cult of Muridism is a theme; whoever is armed with that [experience], regardless of the country he goes to, will learn the language. Now, when you go to China you will speak Chinese, because you yourself have to speak to the Chinese [even without knowing the language].
(SenExp02)

In parallel, as evidenced by several individual experiences, given the challenges of continuing education with limited resources, interest in education goes hand in hand with the urge to emigrate to learn a profession, especially in the trading sector, instead of working in agriculture.

In Diafa Douma, the conditions were very difficult. You can't have the life you want. [...] There's no transport. You have to walk long distances even to go to school. That's why we prefer to come here [Dakar] to work so that we can meet our needs and those of our parents.
(SenMig13)

It's very difficult to learn a trade. Here [in Khombole] there's almost no opportunity.
(SenMig06)

It's difficult to learn a trade in the village, because there's simply no vocational school [in Agnam Civol]. It's possible to learn some trades such as tailor, carpenter and mechanic informally, [but] even this is rare.
(SenMig15)

The possibility of continuing studying and vocational training in Dakar are key reasons to migrate...they're also a means to break away from the social obligations of our rural context of living. You have to understand that in my village not everyone could learn a trade. There are a lot of prejudices; often even your parents can ask you not to waste your time. And don't forget that it's hardly possible to work [both] in the fields and in another trade. [...] Leaving [emigrating] is the best thing to do.
(SenMig20)

The interviews with the persons who had recently arrived in Dakar strongly suggest that the need to learn a trade and the lack of vocational training schools in the places of origin are a major reason for migration. These young adults move in a social environment where even in the place of origin, such as the small town of Ndioum, "it's easier to find good primary schools, French-Arab institutes or a college", so the driving motivations change for "people continue to migrate, even abroad" (SenMig07). Whether young adults' aspirations to migrate are nurtured by their expectations of quick success by working initially in the urban trade sector and subsequently in manual labour jobs overseas, as also noted by Newman (2019: 224), "the limited incentive to pursue secondary state schooling is tied to a low evaluation of the economic utility of secondary school diplomas or Senegalese university degrees" insofar as "schools train a large number of pupils for well-paid formal sector jobs which simply do not exist, or which are inaccessible to all but the most affluent elite".

This shift in opinion has taken place in the wake of the progressive replacement of the 1970s myth of the student who is successful in his home country with the figure of the enterprising and courageous emigrant. The local “culture of migration” and the expectations of young men have become increasingly shaped by the dominant male role model of the rich but unschooled migrant.

In our village, there's no one who teaches a trade. There's only a school and agriculture. [...] That's all there is out there.
(SenMig23)

It's very difficult to find a job in our village. For me it's due to the policy of the state which doesn't invest anything in the village, and because these trades, which I quoted to you [tailor and metal welder], aren't rich and there's nobody else that can give young people a job.
(SenMig01)

When I had to leave, I discussed it with all of my family. I told them I was going to drop out of school to learn a trade. I only left after they agreed. I saw this information about Dakar on television. They talked about the profession of driver. I then said to myself that it's easy to go and learn to be a driver in Dakar.
(SenMig26)

The experiences of younger migrants, triggered by a desire to learn a profession rather than to learn at school, mark a generational shift. In contrast, the former migrant population displayed a sturdier life plan, but were less equipped materially and informationally regarding the opportunities and uncertainties of the capital city. Although better educated, the migrants who headed to Dakar more recently picture a population that makes up for the devaluation of schooling with a greater readiness to face the challenges produced by the saturation of the urban labour market as well as a greater inclination to look beyond the national borders.

Here [in Dakar], life is all about getting up and going to earn a living. The world isn't the same [as in the village]. Everyone has to rely on themselves alone to survive. Here the social dimension is perceived as less important whereas in the village we live in a community where there are many misunderstandings between the young people who aspire to change and the adults who are still blind and withdrawn in their shell. Since we can't get along with them, all we can do is try to find some common ground.

Dakar is only a transit point to try to get abroad. We'd like to live in our homelands, but the situation is so difficult and tense that to stay or go back would mean stoking up a lot of issues.
(SenMig30)

Nonetheless, they are willing to seize any sudden opportunity to acquire knowledge or, above all, to earn money quickly. In this perspective, a trade in Dakar could therefore be a stepping stone to migrating.

Further evidence of this divergence is provided by the testimony of one of the interviewees, a long-term settler who originally came to Dakar to pursue his university studies:

No, it's not difficult to learn a trade. [...] The problem is that young people don't want to learn a trade and they want to have money in such a short time. If you want to become a mechanic or a carpenter and you give yourself the means to achieve it, there's no doubt you'll succeed.
(SenMig28)

As one of the key experts noted, it is particularly important to point out how the willingness to make money that is mentioned by several interviewees does not refer solely to the material and economic dimension, but is rather to be understood as an expression of the great social pressure that people are exposed to within their kin group.

For example, you go to the Kolda region with its potential, which has everything in terms of agricultural possibilities, and yet the latest emigration figures point to this region. Which leads me to say that in actual fact we can't talk about poverty, but more the quest for well-being. People wonder how to build a house, how to get married, how to send their parents money, how to get respect and everything leads to the other element which is social pressure. We live in an increasingly materialized environment where when you have the money, you're fine. So, money becomes a determinant of social pressure. And so, this social pressure comes into play if you're in a polygamous family and if you have neighbours who are international [having family members abroad providing remittances] and they start to make alterations to the house. If you aren't very resilient or resistant on certain issues, you'll be tempted to emigrate.
(SenExp01)

Perspectives in agriculture: lands as an inherited challenge

Against this background and the aforementioned differentiation between migrant generations, leaving the areas of origin for Dakar proves to be an unavoidable necessity rather than a choice, as a 23-year-old unemployed man explains.

Certainly, the situation is very difficult, but every young person just wants to be successful at home first of all. We think of [our parents] as people who live in antiquity while the world has changed. They have established social norms, which is to say, they make sure that none of the young people go anywhere and stay working in the village as shepherds but it isn't a law, just their crap. We're forced to evolve and change the mentality in our life and migrate to other horizons hoping to find a better life. They can't stay forever in these positions which have no religious basis.
(SenMig30)

To learn a trade, there must be a lot of shops available. Like me, there are some who come to Dakar to learn a trade. If they aren't making a good living, they return to the village to open a workshop to practise their profession and train young people.
(SenMig13)

The interviews with new settlers appear to confirm earlier studies which emphasized that individual migration is not simply an expression of a general rejection or failure to adapt to an "old" way of life. Rather, it is a coping strategy that attempts to reconcile a willingness to follow personal aspirations with an attempt to creatively ensure the survival and continuity of the socio-economic context of origin. Unlike those who arrived during the early and more promising phase of urban development, the recent migrants display a flexible attitude which combines an awareness of the challenges of professional prospects in Dakar and does not rule out a future commitment to return to the place of origin to cultivate the family land.

Interestingly, this propensity suggests patterns of mobility that are reminiscent of the "noorane" and historical patterns of seasonal migration (rural-urban or urban-urban). However, as noted by Zhang (2018: 201), while once return migration was considered the end or opposite of a migratory journey, "return migrations are now seen as components of a grounded, temporally differentiated circularity" alternating with moments of immobility. Far from being linear and prospectively clear-cut, the trajectories of migration (to the capital or abroad) and the aspirations from which they spring, are temporally and spatially unstable and fragmented. This is due to intersecting factors pertaining to the relationship between internal and international migrations. Despite recent attempts at diversification, agriculture remains the predominant production sector in rural Senegal. Many of the young people interviewed are landowners through family inheritance. Contrary to a more common understanding, their responses confirm a willingness to return to agriculture as an alternative livelihood, but strong reservations remain due to a lack of adequate and well-planned government support.

For me, agriculture is a very suitable job for young people. If the state supports young people and gives them the means to work, you'll see that the country will develop.
(SenMig19)

It's the government that marginalizes this profession. Most farmers sell their produce in informal weekly markets (louma). The prices the government has set don't suit the farmers. Sometimes we'd like the government to offer us better. They fix the price; the producers have their price and the traders also have their prices. But it should be up to the producer to see what suits him.

(SenMig27)

A young person can't succeed in life through farming. The first reason for saying this is that the state has our lands fully under its control. The second reason is that adults won't give us more room, more responsibility. They don't want to involve us in the decision-making.

(SenMig30)

Although agriculture is portrayed by the authorities as a high growth sector, the implementation of the REVA (Retour Vers l'Agriculture) and PRODAC (Programme des Domaines Agricoles Communautaires) plans seems to hint at difficulties in formulating effective responses to the specific regional and local issues. As underlined by one interviewee, further obstacles that prevent recently arrived migrants in Dakar from engaging seriously, even if only periodically, in working the land relate to the hierarchical relationships and intergenerational divergences of interests concerning land management.

[By the villagers] we aren't known to be big farmers in the area. [...] our main problem with agriculture is that our father is too stingy, he doesn't want to take risks by cultivating several hectares. We asked him to buy just enough suitable means, and then we would have been able to cultivate the land. But it was a losing battle from the outset.

(SenMig30)

As supported by recent studies, the possibilities of young people's integration in the agricultural sector "consistently comes up against the power relations and weight of the elders. According to recent surveys in the Groundnut Basin, the Delta and the Niayes regions, 51% of young people who had migrated to an urban area did not possess any resource (land or livestock) in the locality of origin" (Ba et al., 2017: 32).

Along with intergenerational competition, the lack of proper financial and technical means to cultivate the land is also mentioned as the main reason boosting the migrants' propensity to out-migrate.

In the village, we have only one activity, which is agriculture, and it's a sector that has problems. These problems are due to the lack of means, which pushed us to come to Dakar to earn our living.

(SenMig05)

We...our family, have a lot of land, but if you don't have the proper means, you can't harvest good crops [and] you'll cultivate at a loss. Obviously, agriculture is a suitable job for young people, for me the state must support young people in farming to reduce the unemployment rate and the rural exodus. Agriculture allows a country to develop, you imagine in Senegal, there's so much land to cultivate and this will allow young people to earn money. Instead of staying in the cities and being a street vendor or doing a stupid trade that doesn't make much money, the state must help the young people to cultivate the land in the villages.

(SenMig09)

This is why it's important for us that the authorities make substantial financial resources available to us. In addition, we have the most fertile land in Senegal. What you can get from farming in a month if all the conditions are right is not comparable to what you can get from months of work in Dakar. With a single season you can practically have 1,500,000 FCFA and what kind of job do you think could offer you this amount in such a short time? It isn't because agriculture doesn't appeal to young people but, in reality, it's the material and financial means that are really lacking.

(SenMig20)

Environmental changes

Among the interviewees, environmental changes are neither mentioned nor apparently perceived as a direct factor in migration. On the other hand, as noted by a key expert, insofar as “growing peanuts wouldn’t pay off”, a rural crisis coupled with an environmental crisis may provide a “plausible hypothesis” for why many people left for the city (SenExp01). However, it does not yet seem possible to make an adequate empirical assessment of the social and environmental processes that may influence the decision to leave the areas of origin. Further research is required to unravel the ambiguities of the relationship between international migration and environmental change.

The observations of a key expert give an interesting contribution, which is also in line with the aforementioned studies highlighting how the internal migration triggered by environmental changes does not usually lead to land abandonment but to short-term mobility patterns.

It’s a question [how far environmental and climatic factors lead people to leave?] that has raised a lot of discussion but if you see the evolution of international migration, it’s not necessarily linked [to climate change] because climate change is a long-term development. I’ve already said that in the 1970s and 80s, there was drought. In the main part, we weren’t talking about climate change because climate change can be measured over the long term and [if] there’s a deterioration in environmental conditions, that initially leads to migration. When we also look at the volume of these migrations, in practice what we can see in these data is instead [that] the migrations which are linked to climatic deteriorations are migrations of a short duration and a short distance. It’s well established that international migration requires a lot of resources. When there are conditions that bring populations to extreme situations, they don’t have the minimum resources necessary to go on international migration and go to Libya: you have to take a bus, have money and pay a smuggler. These are minimum resources that someone who is in a precarious situation does not have and cannot pay to start an international migration. So, the only solution for these young people who come from the countryside is to be street vendors (in the cities), to earn without the slightest investment, because they just do not have this investment.
(SenExp02)

3.5 Mechanisms of migration

In the 1970s, during the years of severe drought, the processes of internal migration from the Senegal River valley (whose main centres are Saint-Louis and Matam) and from the major groundnut-growing regions (Kaolack, Fatick, Louga, Diourbel...) to urban areas were mainly the result of a livelihood strategy put into practice by households in order to adjust to these conditions. Instead, information from the interviews supports the idea that more recent migrations are in many cases based on the indirect experiences of neighbouring relatives and friends as earlier pioneers of migration to Dakar and abroad. An important role is also played by easier information-sharing facilitated by social media platforms.

Ever since we’ve known, there have always been emigrants, since long before we were even born. And this is a phenomenon that still continues to exist. People are divided about their impact and their work back home. On the one hand, we can say that they really have helped to develop it here as some are considered models of success but on the other hand, we could deny that they’ve made any difference because our old ways of living and thinking endure as the world changes.
(SenMig30)

This interviewee and the following ones confirm the central role that relatives and friends play in internal migration, not only in providing initial accommodation in the capital, but also in providing guidance and, less frequently, access to a first job.

Yes, they [relatives] really helped me in every way! They did everything a son would do for his parents. They offered me advice as a person coming from a village to Dakar. [...] It was my uncle who hosted me in his house and took me into his painting team and taught me the trade.
(SenMig03)

Yes, I remember...I had to come to Dakar to be able to continue my studies. But where I went wasn't a choice but an obligation. I didn't have another relative who could accommodate me other than my uncle. Moreover, we also live with other people from my village in the same district of Guédiawaye. (SenMigo7)

It was thanks to one of my friends that I received guidance. He was the one who told me to come; he helped me get a job through his contacts and thanks to one of his acquaintances. That's how it happened. (SenMig23)

Similarly, also in the context of international migration outside Africa, the family as well as friendship networks are a key factor in the migration process. In addition, the increasing difficulty of accessing regular channels of emigration goes hand in hand with a greater need to rely on informal networks of people known as "swallows", who not only mediate the material organization of the migration trajectory or process, but also make the migrants' aspiration a reality.

There are a lot of people who have emigrated but most of them travel legally. They [the 'swallows' or mediators] make sure all arrangements are made because they're supposed to welcome you. Wherever you go, you don't leave without having a 'swallow'. You must first have a safe contact before disembarking. Before leaving, you make sure you have a family or a host, a contact person so that you can reach your destination.

There's no doubt that before I leave [for Europe] I'll have to get things ready as needed, that is, have a person to contact once I arrive there who'll allow me to integrate better. I'd prefer to go to Spain or Italy... it's absolutely normal to try the adventure when you see your brothers leave and come back bringing positive changes. (SenMigo6)

The increasing use of social media technologies among kin and migrants plays an ever more central role in shaping migration decisions by strengthening weak ties between geographically dispersed individuals. This is even more the case since migration policies have been tightened and borders closed.

The list [of relatives abroad] is long, there are many. I have a cousin on my mother's side who's abroad. And an uncle who lives with his whole family abroad. My cousins I told you about earlier who are in Keur Massar are practically all abroad. [...] We talk to each other very often. It's just that these days I haven't got WhatsApp anymore. (SenMig24)

Yes, I have relatives who are abroad, there's my cousin who is in France and I speak to constantly on the phone on WhatsApp and two other cousins who are in Spain and the United States. (SenMigo8)

It's not like it used to be: when you emigrated, you could have gone several months without hearing from anyone. Now you can talk and see each other straight away. [...] I chat with them [relatives] very often over the social networks, especially by WhatsApp. (SenMigo7)

It is also interesting to note that the Murid Brotherhood, which has historically played a central role in providing organizational and social ties fostering the circular migration model (both internally and internationally) as well as reproducing transnational social networks, is proving capable of reframing its social role in relation to the changing patterns of Senegalese migration.

If you look, there are a lot of people who have WhatsApp groups; most people have cell phones. Like the brotherhoods that have WhatsApp networks in which not all the members reside in Senegal. There are people who are in western countries and everywhere, even in Africa. So, from this network, people are getting information, in a number of cases even from Italy, from France, etc. And whoever's on the other side informs them daily. All means of communication are used in order to be able to put yourself in the best possible position to emigrate. The religious brotherhoods are a perfect example. We're always sharing information.

(SenExp03)

3.6 Reasons for the choice of destination

Despite the reduction in job opportunities and livelihood conditions, among the young generation of migrants, Dakar still remains a central stage in the migration routes. The latest statistics from 2013 show that Dakar is "a point of attraction for all migration departures" (SenExp03). As also confirmed by several interviewees, the capital is the main point of reference not only for internal migration, but also as a springboard for migration abroad.

Most of the people who left our area of origin [the region of Matam] for abroad, left for countries like France, for Central Africa, more precisely for Gabon, and Ivory Coast. As for those people who stay in Senegal, they usually come to Dakar and once in Dakar they look for a way to go abroad.

(SenMig09)

Because there are more opportunities in the cities. Here [in Dakar] there is everything and as a student, you can find casual jobs, outside school hours and there's a lot to discover. You discover new things and you meet new people. On the other hand, in the village, everyone knows each other, people help each other, there's solidarity, people live in safety, you can walk and go anywhere, and people live in a community.

(SenMig08)

Unbalanced economic development between the capital and the hinterland and the state's limited interventions in other regions of Senegal contribute to the fact that Dakar, the capital, still plays a very attractive role in internal migration in Senegal. As mentioned, in the case of internal migrants from the Matam and Casamance regions, the availability of vocational training opportunities, albeit often informal, improved infrastructure and better access to social services prove to be important drivers in moving to Dakar.

The problems in the village are the lack of infrastructure and opportunities that can allow young people to work.

(SenMig06)

The information I had about Dakar was that it's a city where people work...where there is mobility! We're not idle. The people who came back to the village were telling me all the time about the work opportunities in Dakar and that everything is "on the move". They said that everyone [just] works, "rek".

I came to Dakar to have money, to take care of myself, to help my mother and my father and my parents. It's true that I am the youngest in our family, but we're poor. I'd have to fight to be able to succeed [back home].

(SenMig03)

Nonetheless, as suggested by some interviewees, the attractiveness of the capital is enhanced by the visual and material influence of the periodic returns of co-villagers from Dakar as well as by international migrants who feed the popular imagination and foster imitation by showing off fashionable jewellery, new clothes and housing investments.

I heard people say all the time that Dakar is a good place to live and I saw people come back to the village with beautiful things, clothes made from special material [thin rubber or other light material] and they have a good smell, with a good perfume. And they took our girlfriends from us [laughs] and there was a cousin of mine who gave us jerseys and balls every time he came back to the village.

(SenMig01)

Life is good in Dakar...there's more money. We were told that there's a good life here. This is what we're told in the village. In the village you don't wear nice clothes, go out in the evening or have cars. This is what made us dream. This is what we wanted to discover but also to experience.

(SenMig13)

Most of those who have lived in Dakar for a long time do not remember the transition from rural life in the villages to the urban lifestyle. While socially perceived as a simple internal movement within the country, it was experienced as a radical change and a marked separation. "City life and the village are worlds apart" (SenMig15), not only geographically but mostly economically and culturally.

In the village it's difficult to become intelligent, smart...to know the hardships of life; while in the city every day you learn to face the obstacles and adversities of life, such as being swindled. Once you're here [in Dakar], you learn to juggle, to adapt and to be open-minded.

(SenMig11)

There's a big difference between the city and the village. All the entertainment events are happening in the cities, wrestling matches, soccer matches, concerts and dancing parties. In the city, people have companies, big hospitals, important universities and schools. The city is a place that offers opportunities for work, learning and care for people. On the other hand, in the village, there's an ideal living environment, but life is monotonous, people repeat the same things, there's only farming, animal breeding and fishing. It doesn't offer opportunities for young people to be able to work and there are no places of entertainment like in the city.

(SenMig9)

I've learned a lot since I've been here. There are things I got to know here; I had no idea about them when I was in the village. For example, the way of life. You know, when you're in the village, you live in a community. You have the same practices, the same clothing. But when you come here you learn a lot.

(SenMig13)

Nevertheless, as one long-settled interviewee aptly illustrated: "the village is a tree with its roots, while the city is a tree with its fruits" (SenMig15). In other words, although rural life is portrayed as instilled with conventional traditionalism and somehow archaic practices vis-à-vis a more modernized urbanity, both are understood and experienced as complementary components of the individual's life trajectory.

People had the information that some said it was an easy and pleasant life while others said the opposite, like how difficult life is. Opinions were always different, like they are about being abroad. Each time the emigrants gave us information, we heard them speak out about it. But if you really want to know, this information in no way hinders your desire to leave, besides you're eager to discover the reality.

(SenMig24)

Moreover, having landed in the city, the migrants vacillate between "shame and ambition" (SenMig11); the description of the daily urban experience gradually gives way to the emergence of more ambivalent expectations and social representations of the new context of life in Dakar and abroad and its relationship to the village of origin.

People I knew who had taken the same route gave me all the information I needed. They made us aware of the risks and dangers, but it was a risk you had to take [...]. We've all tried our luck and God will assist us in all circumstances. And unfortunately, we realized that they hadn't lied to us about anything, everything was true. (SenMig20)

City life and the village are two different worlds. In the city, there are a lot of people, noise, jobs. All the people who go to a country stay in the cities because they offer work opportunities. In the city, there are schools, universities and hospitals, there's also a lack of solidarity and security, hence the existence of thefts and attacks. On the other hand, in the village, there's absolutely nothing, no infrastructure, no factories or businesses to allow young people to work. In the village, people also see that there is solidarity. (SenMig15)

As you know, these are two very different places. In the city you have all the possibilities with huge advantages, good schools, important hospitals, the best training schools and the possibility of getting a job. Conversely, the village is a closed, quiet place with a monotonous life that offers no possibilities for people. This is what explains this rural exodus to the cities. In addition, I would add that in the city, there is insecurity, banditry and youth delinquency. Instead, the village is a peaceful place where the young people are well educated. (SenMig07)

Although the arrival in the capital, as the interviewees explained, is in many cases only the last and most recent experience in previous paths of mobility to other cities (Kédougou, Sabodala, Kaolack, Tambacounda) or even countries (Guinea-Bissau, Cape Verde, Ivory Coast or Gabon), bitter discoveries and unfulfilled or protracted expectations shape their current experience as well as their future propensities to seek new opportunities abroad:

Can you imagine? You can stay in Dakar for days or months looking for work without finding something to do. And even worse, a lot of people who come to the cities end up being robbed of their money. (SenMig11)

I thought there was a comfortable life in Dakar. When I finished high school, I had only one vision – to go to university – because I believed that if you finished your studies, you'd get what you want. But it was a big disappointment. (SenMig12)

3.7 Expectations and current situation

In the theoretical framework of the FUME project, the urban context is understood either as a permanent destination or as a place of passage for people, many of whom aim to migrate abroad.

If someone comes to Dakar, it's just the beginning of the journey. It's the beginning of the search for an opportunity to go to a western country. Step by step ... In Dakar we try to earn a living little by little and if we're given an opportunity ... we take our chance! [Living in Dakar] is also an opportunity to acquire some experience so that once you arrive in Europe, you won't have certain problems or difficulties. If you have a chance to be in the capital and you try to understand a lot of things, once outside [abroad], it'll be a great advantage. (SenMig24)

However, the decision to migrate internationally, to return to the place of origin, or to remain in the city is mostly influenced by the degree to which the urban experience has met the pre-migratory expectations. In other words, the city becomes a field of assessment of individual aspirations which constantly swing between confidence and uncertainty. Especially in the memory of long-term migrants in Dakar, the city offers a range of health, logistic, employment and socio-cultural facilities that more isolated and less developed rural areas of Senegal cannot match:

The city is very different from the village, in the city you can find everything, big hospitals for treatment, companies and factories that offer job opportunities to young people, and it's very easy to get work in comparison with the village. The village also has its advantages: there's a jovial atmosphere, everyone is together and the people help each other well and there's security.

(SenMigo1)

Overall, as noted by several interviewees, the numerous years spent in the capital have brought important material life changes and achievements which are nevertheless perceived, in many cases, as limited to the level of family subsistence.

What has changed in my life is that now I work, got married and I have a child.

(SenMigo10)

Picture: Seth Doyle/Unsplash.com

Since being here in Dakar, I have a job that allows me to earn something. Even if it's not enough, I manage to meet some of my family's most basic needs.

(SenMig21)

I've had a lot of positive changes in my life here [in Dakar] but I haven't achieved my goals. I only manage somehow to feed my family.

(SenMig20)

Frankly, I'm not complaining. Thank God! I have to be honest, this isn't what I really hoped for, but I manage with what I have. Life isn't as easy as you think before coming here, but things need to be done gradually. I'll hang onto this job until I find another much higher earning one.

(SenMig24)

Conversely, rather limited socio-economic advancements, or even a "frank disillusionment due to the lack of changes" (SenMig18) seem to characterize the experience of those young migrants who arrived more recently.

Yes, there's been a small positive change because I work and earn enough to live. The money allows me to meet my needs. Today, I can buy food. I can buy clothes. With the little money I earn I manage to help my parents. I see a little progress. When I arrived, I couldn't do my present job. But it's only a small step forward.

(SenMig26)

The individual's socio-demographic profile appears to shape the first experience of living in Dakar. Most frequently, regardless the scale of the network of relationships that the migrants can rely on, those with little state education face a greater challenge to find a stable and decently paid job. As the following interviewee puts it:

Personally, I think everyone has their own worries even though my friends don't often talk about them. As far as I'm concerned, I had difficulty finding a job in the city. I started out as a street vendor after two years and then I was recruited as a salesperson in a food store for about five years.

(SenMig17)

At the beginning, it was very difficult for me, because I was a day labourer. After that an employee left for another depot and I was given the cart. It was difficult at first with the cart because I couldn't sell the products and you get paid if you sell. I didn't know the circuit.

(SenMig05)

From one ill-paying job to the next, the migrants struggle to make ends meet in Dakar. However, as they pointed out, even though their condition might be shared by their friends and fellows, it is rarely mentioned. Men and women alike are not willing to talk about or describe their situation due to the shame and social stigma attached to it. As suggested by the following account, this woman would have preferred not to talk about her first activity of selling water on the street when she arrived in Dakar; but that very same activity has enabled her to open her current business, a breakfast shop, of which she is prouder.

Just a month ago I was selling water on the streets. I bought this container for 10,000 francs so that I could keep water bags to resell. Sometimes it worked, sometimes it didn't. You should never be discouraged in life. It's thanks to selling water sachets that I was able to buy materials to start selling breakfasts.

(SenMig18)

A wider social network and more opportunities...along with more expenses

As acknowledged by several interviewees, the urban experience turns into the opportunity to establish, widen or strengthen some social relations.

Certainly, living here has allowed me to get to know new people or to know some better. Somehow, I am realizing every day, and more and more, that everything people told me about Dakar is true.
(SenMig07)

There are more opportunities here [in Dakar]. [...] You discover new things and you meet new people, whereas in the village, everyone knows each other.
(SenMig08)

Moreover, although Dakar may certainly offer a wide range of employment and educational opportunities that enable higher wages compared to rural areas, these favourable aspects have a downside in that expenses also rise. Food expenditure, rent, transport costs and clothing all go to increase the socio-economic pressure on migrants who have a hard time saving money and helping their families in their places of origin.

Life in the village is easier than in the city. Indeed, what you spend for one person here in town can feed an entire family in the village. For example, if I spend 2,000 francs in one day, those 2,000 francs could feed my family in the village. But also, in terms of housing, in town if you don't have a place to stay, you have to find a room to rent or something, whereas in the village there's no rent even if you're a foreigner, you can find somewhere to sleep without paying anything.
(SenMig12)

Despite the evident difficulties of making ends meet, these interviewees do not consider their life and working experience in Dakar to be penalizing. Overall, life in Dakar grants migrants a relatively higher net return and a greater possibility of supporting their families compared to their previous experiences in the places of origin.

More opportunities but also an unsafe urban environment

Despite being appreciated thanks to the greater opportunities of employment and business, for many interviewees life in Dakar is also heavily conditioned by an increased level of insecurity. Especially among those with family and children, the recent and increasing episodes of child abductions and street murders have boosted the social perception of the capital as a hostile environment.

For me, the city is stressful, especially when your family is living there with you. Sometimes I'm distressed by the level of insecurity, you might hear on the radio that a child has been kidnapped and, I'm very afraid, and it totally gets me down. On the other hand, in the village you're safe, you don't even care about these things. The only problem is that there's nothing, no infrastructure.
(SenMig18)

In the city there's insecurity, while in the villages there's more security. Because in the villages, you can reach your house at any time and go to bed without any worries, but here in the city you can't come back at certain times. This morning a friend of mine was assaulted at 9 am, he was robbed of 3 million [francs] and stabbed. In the village, the only problem they have is the land. The people in the village are much more united than in the city but in the city, mind, it's every man for himself.
(SenMig11)

3.8 Future intentions - return, stay or further migration

The interviews examined so far highlight how the trajectories of mobility are in most cases the outcome of an ongoing evaluation of intertwined subjective/collective choices and objective living conditions (see also Cissokho et al., 2021). Thus, there are no solely external, economic or political causalities or exclusively subjective motivations that boost the willingness to leave the place of origin and, as discussed below, to consider, at a second stage, migration abroad.

When asking about motivations to migrate or to remain in Senegal, both existential and contextual dimensions must be addressed and set out at the same time.

Among the interviewees, the following evidence confirms that the majority display a pronounced enthusiasm and propensity to migrate, as a way to access additional monetary and material resources that are increasingly hard to accumulate. Only a limited number of interviewees expressed a preference to remain in Senegal. More generally, migration propensity is driven by a widespread experience of a lack of credible living prospects, combined with an increasing perception of living in a hostile environment, alongside the success shown by migration and reflected by those who migrated. Overall, the evidence suggests that migration aspirations are higher among those people with low schooling and among university graduates who are in a state of limbo in Dakar, working occasionally or waiting to find a decent job to earn a living.

However, most of the interviewees' discourses and experiences suggest a mismatch between the open manifestation of a desire to migrate abroad and their operational or practical decision to take concrete action. In this respect, the discouragement mostly seems linked to the obstacles posed by unfavourable international migration policies and regulations. Despite the ambivalent understanding behind the perceptions of the crisis situation in Europe, among the interviewees the propensity to migrate does not exclude an awareness of how much this situation affects migrants' lives.

The data available support the idea that the diverse timing of the migrants' arrival in Dakar differentially influences their aspirations and motivations to leave Dakar or to stay in the city.

Leaving to go abroad or returning: the important thing is to be "on the move"

While some factors influence migration aspirations more than others, the interviewees mostly agree on the idea that emigrating becomes an unescapable option with respect to remaining inasmuch as it offers an opportunity to overcome the overall insecurity of everyday life. The feelings and difficulties of envisaging options for remaining in Senegal appear particularly strong among those who have recently arrived in Dakar and are somehow disillusioned by the dearth of working opportunities available.

What will change my mind is having something [...] and being able to take care of myself and my family. If I received support in Senegal, I'd prefer to stay rather than to emigrate. [...]. But with these inadequate jobs, if I meet someone who offers me the opportunity to travel, I'll go [abroad].
(SenMig07)

As long as my parents or my family are counting on me to meet their primary and secondary needs, I think I'll have no choice. Staying [in Dakar or abroad] until retirement will become an obligation for me and for anyone in the same situation.
(SenMig17)

Honesty, I'm not willing to stay [in Senegal] any longer unless I had enough money and I could embark on my projects without fighting for a job! ... I need to get past this painful, ongoing [situation of] precariousness.
(SenMig28)

Among the migrants who settled more recently in Dakar, the desire to migrate is fuelled by an overlapping mix of disappointments, enthusiastic ambitions and opposing aspirations. In fact, whether or not the propensity to migrate abroad is a shared intention of all interviewees, those who arrived recently also contemplate a return, even if it is only periodically, to work in agriculture as a way to tackle the growing challenges of a saturated labour market.

If I have the equipment [for farming], it'll do for me. It all depends on the material. If we have the right material, I think it'll be within our reach. I have this project in mind. I want to broaden the area to cultivate and then find the appropriate material.
(SenMigo2)

Agriculture is fundamental for a country and young people should do it [...]. If they moved to the countryside, they could find employment. However, in Saint-Louis, there are only two companies, GDS [Grands Domaines du Sénégal] and CLS [Collecte Localisation Satellites], and these two companies can't take on all the young people.
(SenMigo8)

I'll be willing to stay in Senegal, as long as I have enough money. This will allow me to make my investments in agriculture.
(SenMigo6)

On the other hand, the annoyance with the national authorities, the perception of being trapped in a state of immobility, along with an understanding of "travelling" as a means to enhance individual knowledge or a possibility of "conceiving a future" away from home, all of this comes into play in fostering the propensity to migrate abroad:

When these people are aware of the situation and realize that the government is only there to rip people off, of course people will look to go elsewhere. They [the politicians] all need throwing out.
(SenMig30)

I'd like to venture out but also to find out what's going on elsewhere...I'd especially like to increase my knowledge. Once people go back to the fold, they can sensitize other young people who wish to emigrate.
(SenMig29)

The interviewees also point out that it is often the visual and material evidence of the achievements of returnees and their tendency to show no real interest in returning permanently to Senegal that motivates people to emigrate in turn:

I don't know...if it's difficult or not I can't even say; if it's difficult [to live abroad], why do they return after their holidays in Europe and what is it that prevents them from returning to their countries once and for all?
(SenMigo3)

I don't know enough about Europe. But I think there's social security, good hospitals and wealth.
(SenMig12)

In parallel, while the increasing feminization of migration which began two decades ago is certainly the main demographic change in the patterns of Senegalese mobility, the phenomenon is nonetheless the sign of a sense of frustration over unequal social opportunities. The increased participation of women in the migration

processes can be understood as a social transformation that allows women to migrate without husbands. Once migration is no longer the exclusive preserve of men, women claim the right and willingness to embark on the adventure of migration, but not in view of family reunification. As one key expert recognized:

In the feminization of migration many sociological factors have played a role, especially the progressive tendency to migrate to urban areas [where] society has less and less control over the individual... [this] has led women to become more and more empowered in the urban environment, society has less and less control over the individual as well as women, and so women also decide to leave.
(SenExp02)

They still mostly emigrate through the usual channels, namely in the context of family reunification, but this practice has evolved and now it is less influenced by socio-ethnic determinants. Since the centre of departure for migration is increasingly often cities, people see that cultures are becoming more and more hybridized (cultural differences between ethnic groups are being brought closer and closer together). I believe the tendency is that socio-cultural factors and constraints have less weight ... because a Haalpulaar won't be any more prone to leave than a Serer.
(SenExp02)

Interestingly, the narratives suggest how the growing presence of women in migration marks a change in women's social perceptions and attitudes, not only towards migration practices but more importantly in relation to the organization of the Senegalese. As pointed out by this woman interviewed in a salesroom in the Gibraltar neighbourhood:

People used to see the men going to work and the woman staying at home. This life is so hard that women can no longer stay at home. In our society, it's the woman who has to stay at home, take care of her children and the housework. It isn't the same now as women leave their children at home to look for work even if this isn't what we want as housewives but it's obvious. And with COVID-19, which was hard for us.
(Sall, 2021)

It is worth recalling the words of the shopkeeper in Tally Bou Bess in the neighbourhood of Pikine to illustrate how, as the young woman sees it, migration becomes an extraordinary means of affirming oneself and claiming social rights.

[I wish to emigrate abroad] because, I think where I'm going is better than where I come from. [...] The poorest in these countries [abroad] have better living conditions than us; for example, housekeepers are paid better abroad than in Senegal, because they know the true value of these women and have total respect for them.
(SenMig11)

Aspiring but not planning to migrate

Europe is a good destination, there are many emigrants who choose it. Their [The Europeans'] problem is that they are a little racist and reluctant when it comes to the procedures for issuing or obtaining a visa.
(SenMig29)

While it goes without saying that getting documents (passport and visa) is a key step towards the realization of a project, the interviewees' narratives also suggest that the concrete effort to come into possession of them, more or less legally, becomes a litmus test indicating whether or not the migration project has entered a serious stage.

... the biggest difficulties to face will be getting a visa and being in good standing, having residency or a paper which allows you to move and work.
(SenMig29)

I haven't been abroad yet, but what is difficult is getting a visa and I see people going through the desert, ... they're so tired, they're in danger. In general, the smugglers eat up their money, which puts them in a difficult situation.
(SenMig03)

While the aspiration to emigrate abroad, especially to Europe or the United States, underlies the discourses of most of the interviewees, only a few answered that they were actually able to go through with it. None of the interviewees had gathered the necessary information or had really planned the organization of the trip. The most frequent answers to the question about what measures they had taken to get ready for the trip were the following:

I don't have a passport or a visa ... We're men! We'll improvise and God will help us whatever the situation is.
(SenMig29)

No, I don't have a passport yet, so I'll try to get accepted at university and then I'll get ready for my trip by looking for a passport and then a visa...that is to say, I'll go along the normal route.
(SenMigo8)

The first step to take is obviously to get a visa, but not everyone is so lucky. You need the money to get it.
(SenMig27)

Affirmation of the willingness to leave immediately, if possible, via legal channels of migration, is a dominant statement among the majority of the interviewees. However, the lack of any concrete action or initiatives in this direction makes it evident that migration via a legal route is perceived as an unattainable dream rather than a planned project.

Most potential migrants see their plans to migrate as a temporary experience, allowing them to earn enough money to return home and meet their more urgent needs, namely to improve their lives and social status. The answers of several interviewees confirm the difficulty in imagining and figuring out future life choices and possibilities.

I could stay there for ten years, until I have enough funds to come back, invest in my country and participate in its development.
(SenMig28)

[I would go] ... to Spain, or to France. As soon as I earned enough money to improve my living conditions, then I'd go back home, ... once I get my papers.
(SenMig29)

In general, an important point is professional training or "avoir un métier", which is a motivation to move from rural areas or small towns, and a prerequisite for trying to move abroad. Education (in the sense of having completed primary, secondary or higher education) is not considered an advantage by most interviewees. Even when schools were available, few of the interviewees attended it at all, or they dropped out. Many emphasize the central role of knowing a trade and obtaining vocational training, much more than the importance of a general education or schooling. However, even though these could be discriminating factors in a globalized world and in the European labour markets, in Senegal they are still difficult to come by.

Fragmented trajectories and informal routes

Dakar's enduring significant role as a place of passage en route to Europe is accompanied by a progressive worsening and uncertainty of the daily living conditions in this urban area and a tightening of EU policies restricting the movements of non-EU people to and within Europe.

It was from there, from the mid-1980s to the 1990s, when there was the crisis that the Europeans now started to tighten the screws by putting visa systems in place. So, these are the reasons why the situation started to get tougher. On the Senegalese side or the African side, drought led to talking about environmental factors. The latter also pushed people to emigrate, to leave their places of origin to go to Dakar. Once in Dakar, most work in the informal sector and when they have the possibility, they'll leave for either African or western countries. (SenExp03)

The latter account sheds light on the ambivalent influence that is played by a widespread informal working sector. While only granting an unstable income and living conditions of ongoing precariousness, the widespread informal working sector also turns out to be a springboard for people who want to go abroad as much as it serves as a fertile ground to establish a new net of relations for a potential migration and a favourable context to accumulate a first sum of money necessary to travel (see also Fall, 2003).

As described by several interviewees, these changes have resulted in an increasing nonlinearity and fragmentation of both the internal and international migration trajectories. Despite the closed borders, Senegalese emigration continues to seek alternative routes to reach Europe:

Although Europe has barricaded itself and become a sanctuary, it doesn't prevent people from leaving, those who are leaving are looking for different ways ... this hasn't prevented people from continuing to leave, so in any case for me, I don't see any effect. [...] I was telling our friends of the IOM that if they close Libya, people will go through Egypt, through Saudi Arabia and Lebanon and go to Europe. As soon as the Libyan route was closed, the Atlantic Ocean became a viable option again...for all those who take pirogues. (SenExp01)

As already mentioned, while the transnational attitude and circulatory movements of many migrants returning from Europe are often affected by regulatory practices, the difficulties of getting a stable and profitable job in Senegal trigger continuous and unplanned movements within the country.

Many young people emigrated because they were stuck at home not doing anything. This situation drove them to move to other places in order to earn something. Here in Senegal, most of these young people go to Kédougou, Sabodala and Dakar. (SenMig10)

At first, I went to Kaolack to learn a trade. Then I went to Tambacounda. I left there because the life was too hard for me; I didn't have any money or a profitable job. Afterwards I went to Dakar and I started working as a carpenter. (SenMig21)

If a person comes to Dakar, it's just the start of the journey. This is to look for an opportunity to go to western countries. It's one step at a time, people try to make a living little by little, and if the opportunity is given to us, people take their chance. It's also an opportunity to gain some experience so that once you arrive in Europe, you may not come up against certain walls. If you're in the capital and understand a lot of things, then that will be a big advantage once you're outside. (SenMig24)

However, the social perception of Dakar as a prospective stepping stone to international migration is also blurred by the experience of those people who have not managed to go abroad after staying in the city for a while. Indeed, more and more frequently, the trajectories of potential migrants do not seem to originate in Dakar, but directly in other minor urban contexts in Senegal, or in coastal or even rural areas. This phenomenon is characterized by a progressive informalization of the migration initiatives to reach Europe, which are taking place further and further away from the capital, on the coasts of the region of the Petite Côte, Senegal River valley and Casamance, as well as in the central (e.g., Kaolack) and eastern border regions (e.g., Tambacounda). And more importantly, as aptly noted by a key expert, the continuous search for alternative and more and more informal routes means that there will be more irregular migration.

... the biggest challenges, people must speak frankly to the countries of the north, the destination countries, but they don't listen to us. When there are restrictions on entering their territories, there will always be irregular or illegal migration, because people will always try to leave.
(SenExp01)

This change in attitude, which conveys a dip in the appeal of the Senegalese capital, suggests the idea that migrating does not stem so much from a longing for a better place or for better opportunities, but rather from experiencing the sense of a complete lack of opportunities to earn a decent living, and therefore the need to leave. And in the absence of the necessary means or contacts, irregular migration becomes the most popular option:

[...] they lack the money to pay for air travel. Migrating by pirogue is risky but costs less.
(SenMig29)

Perils of the trajectories and social death

In a society characterized by the polygamous organization of family relationships, the pressure to assert oneself as a social resource often becomes an unbearable challenge. In this regard, a concrete explanation is given in the interview with a key expert who is directly involved in the fight against illegal or illicit migration.

There is social pressure, in the family itself, with polygamy for example. Often among wives, when a son is in Europe, he works and sends money, his mother is well regarded in the family. But if you stay at home, you aren't given any consideration in the family because you don't make a contribution. No respect, even if you're the eldest. You don't even know what's going on in the family. So, if a young man experiences these conditions, he may one day say to himself that it's no longer worthwhile staying here, why stay here in Senegal; it's better to die than to stay here. In one of our awareness campaigns, a young man told me, "I understand what you're telling us, but I know that I have a 90% chance of dying at sea, 5% of arriving in Europe and 5% of being repatriated, but I'm going to leave because I can't stay here anymore because of the verbal abuse I'm getting in my house and in the neighbourhood."
(SenExp06)

Most interviewees are well aware of the dangers of the migration routes as well as of the precarious conditions of life exposed by some migrants abroad. However, faced with a country that can neither guarantee economic development nor give its citizens the opportunity to rise socially and reproduce their family relationships, it leads people to fear poverty more than death.

At present, after several years [in Dakar] I could say people aren't afraid of death, but of poverty. Dying to ensure yourself and others better conditions and benefiting from it is a noble act for many young people.
(SenMig27)

Everyone knows that [emigration by sea across the Mediterranean] isn't safe, but if you see people that keep taking these routes it's because they're desperate and have no choice. There are times when dying is the least of your worries. As you can see here, people are trying to get by in spite of the difficulties while the state doesn't stop stalking and chasing us. These are the reasons why people leave by sea or across the desert. (SenMig26)

[Emigrating by sea [the Atlantic Ocean] or through the Mediterranean] ... it's all the same. Risks are everywhere; people know full well, but when the time to go comes, it becomes impossible to stay. (SenMig29)

If you don't have documents, you can't have a job. People can sleep in the streets; people can't go back. This is the difficulty [they're facing]. It's a bit hard. This is [why] Europe if you don't have documents and you don't have a job, you risk having a hard time living there. (SenMig26)

Our families depend entirely on us, so we must be prepared to sacrifice ourselves for them so that they can live in good conditions. No matter what the obstacle, a man should always be able to overcome it. (SenMig29)

Some Senegalese are in a good situation and others are not; sometimes some are victims of assassinations and others are escaping dangerous situations. The formalities are not easy, especially for the illiterate people ... and you know, most of the emigrants are illiterate. (SenMig27)

Despite the awareness of the well-known dangers connected to the migration journey or the miserable conditions faced by some migrants abroad, many people consider the possibility of migrating irregularly because they fear a social rather than physical death: the difficulty of succeeding in the social context in which they live (degli Uberti, 2014).

Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic seems to have increased the socio-economic difficulties, triggering different, intertwined effects on the internal mobility of individuals towards the region of Dakar, one of the areas mostly affected by the infection, and the propensity to emigrate abroad.

Yes, it [the COVID-19 pandemic] has changed a lot of things! ... because parents and relatives from localities of origin no longer want to come to Dakar. Interurban transport was temporarily interrupted. ... Because the regions of the country were suddenly sealed off and traders couldn't move, let alone emigrate out of the country. People are no longer moving because of the restrictions and the curfew. The pandemic has affected many sectors financially and morally too and therefore I think people are getting more and more tempted to move abroad. (SenMig28)

COVID-19 has in no way diminished young people's desire to go outside [abroad]. That's for sure. (SenMig21)

The mobility restrictions imposed by the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic and the effects it had on the networks of social relations and the labour market system, have resulted in a heightening of employment insecurity which has made people think about emigration even more often than before.

Since COVID appeared, people don't have any work; many people have lost their jobs because their bosses don't have the money to pay their employees any longer...that's why people make the decision to go to other countries. It's mostly today that people want to emigrate [abroad]. (SenMig23)

COVID-19 and its restrictions have caused many people to lose their jobs. I'm in the dressmaking sector; since get-togethers have been prohibited, the orders linked to weddings and baptisms have dropped. Look at me, I've turned into a doughnut seller to get by. I think all sectors are affected. Quite a few of my friends who worked in restaurants and the tourism sector have lost their jobs. Also those who live abroad, in Europe, have suffered due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

...and so, we end up going the illegal route, taking the pirogues like the young people who wish to reach Spain. We hope that Spanish people need new hands to work since they have lost so many human lives.
(SenMig10)

Interestingly the latter interviewee discloses a peculiar way of looking at the impact of COVID-19 pandemic on Europe as a sign in favour of emigration. Far from being an isolated case, this view appears to be shared by several interviewees.

The pandemic has brought clandestine emigration back up [...], perhaps it's due to the deaths in Europe and the need for new workers that young people in Senegal are leaving.
(SenMigo8)

It should be noted that recently during the first waves of emigration a lot of young people took the pirogues to reach Europe because they thought that the Europeans needed new hands. I, too, talking to you, was ready to go but unfortunately, I didn't have enough money at the time.
(SenMig19)

Taking into account the hiatus between migration aspirations and concrete plans to move that characterizes the behaviour of most of the interviewees, the following considerations offer a pointed synthesis and interpretative lens through which to reframe the discussion of the future scenarios of emigration from Senegal:

I think in the future more and more people will leave. Because if people can't find anything to do in this country, they'll just leave. People only talk about leaving and that the risk doesn't matter. If I could go today, I would.
(SenMig26)

The best solution to solve the problem would be to facilitate migration, to make visas accessible and to create the conditions for circular migration on the basis of agreements between countries. This is how these people can leave and come back quietly and easily by signing memoranda of understanding.
(SenExpo4)

3.9 Beyond Europe

The evidence highlights that past and future migration intentions are not so much determined by a specific plan (a migratory project) but influenced by the possibilities envisaged by individual memories and stories of migration or by the prospective horizons of opportunities and circumstances opened up by day-to-day experiences. So, very often there are no specific or concrete plans regarding a specific destination.

I have friends who have travelled through Libya to reach Europe. They were with us here but preferred to go through the desert. Their story just makes you give up [on the idea of] going through Libya. You tell yourself it's not worth it.
(SenMig25)

When they left, they went to Mali, then to Agadez, Niger. Between Niger and Libya, they went through some really terrible things. I don't know everything, but they experienced hunger. They were captured by the Libyans. There are people who died due to starvation. Really, this is the last-ditch solution. Taking a pirogue to go to Europe means risking your life. I think that in order to travel safely, you have to do it properly. Going by sea or through the desert is a risk. But those who do it, certainly have no choice or are just in a hurry.
(SenMig20)

As for me ... the first time I left I went to Guinea-Bissau. It was for a cashew nut campaign. I stayed for almost three months [...] Then I went to Cape Verde where I only lasted a month because of visa problems. Then I was in Guinea-Bissau again but this time I only stayed one week. It was only later that I returned to the village [Liayel close to Kolda] and from there I tried to reach Libya directly.
(SenMig20)

Today, places like Dubai and China are increasingly sought after by young people. These places offer opportunities for young people to work and earn a lot of money; more and more young people are migrating to these countries.
(SenMigo8)

Although most of the migration networks established with emigrants abroad (e.g., friends or relatives) draw trajectories directed towards Europe, the potential destination countries of Senegalese migrants are very diverse, ranging from sub-Saharan Africa to North or South America, and more recently East Asia. As already discussed, more and more often the wish to emigrate abroad does not reflect a clear-cut migration project. Instead, the plan (and destination) remains rather vague and is often influenced by foreign people as well (degli Uberti, 2011) because "more and more Europeans are leaving Europe for China in search of a better life" (SenMigo1).

I don't have a specific destination; the best thing is to travel to any country.
(SenMig29)
People mustn't hurry. You just have to bide your time. If your turn comes, you'll leave.
(SenMig25)

This is still the case for a good part of [Europe as an attractive place for Senegalese emigrants]. But that pattern is tending to change. Various emigrants are choosing new destinations: the United States, Canada, Argentina. Senegalese people go also to Dubai, China for trading. However, these are countries that have a very closed reception system.
(SenExp03)

Thus, not only France, Italy, Spain, but also China and the Arab Emirates (together with Ivory Coast, Morocco, Congo and Gabon) are increasingly favoured by the respondents in relation to their social or generational networks: "they have indirect personal experiences of migration that are drawn from kin networks (sisters, brothers, uncles) or close friends" (SenMig10).

When interviewees consider the possibility of migrating to Europe as a realistic prospect, their answers do not display a preferred choice, but they appear rather to be the result of assessing the degree of availability of reliable networks of relations.

The first step to take is to make sure you have a good reception, a person who will help you fit in well.
(SenMig19)

Wherever you go, you don't leave without having a 'swallow' [mediator]. You must first have a safe contact before disembarking. Before leaving, you make sure you have a family or a host, a contact person so that you can reach your destination.
(SenMig16)

When thinking about where to migrate to, my main consideration is that I have three [contacts] outside. A sister and two brothers. The brothers are in France while my sister is in South Africa.
(SenMig22)

Where to migrate? I need to think that there's one of my nephews, who's in France. He's been there since 2006.
(SenMigo2)

Social networks, mostly exemplified by the figure of the returnees, continue to play a key role in mediating migration aspirations and in the concrete organization of departures within and outside the country (both regular and irregular). In this sense, an increasing trust in informal networks is documented as a response to the growing difficulties of accessing regular channels of emigration and to the tightening of European migration policies. Nevertheless, both this second factor and the continuous challenge of adapting to new migration policies and regulations lead to very open and flexible ideas on the choice of destination country such as Italy, for instance.

[The choice of destination] is based on the opportunities at the moment they move from one country to another. Italy has the peculiarity of having a much more informal economy than France. [...]. At the administrative level there's been more tolerance towards workers in the informal sector and street vendors. There are also differences in the Italians' languages and cultures. But overall, it's often according to opportunities that the Senegalese move to a country.
(SenExp03)

Picture: D Ad/Unsplash.com

4. Conclusion

Within the framework of the FUME project, the aim of the field research conducted in Senegal is to explore migration aspirations and trajectories while accounting for the role of Dakar, and how the urban experience often becomes a stepping stone or an anchor that prevents further international movement. The research on migration intentions prompts an exploration of what shapes different migration timelines, by focusing on migrants' experiences according to their time of arrival in Dakar: initially those coming from rural areas and arriving recently (less than five years ago), those who have stayed for a long period in Dakar (five to nine years) and those who are long-term settlers (ten years or more). The research has not delved into the migration motivation patterns of Dakar natives.

The data collected through the interviews conducted in Senegal provide valuable information on the country's degree of involvement in the international migration process. It clearly emerges how migration is the outcome of trajectories that take place in different spaces and times, where social actors (the potential migrants and their relatives) always evaluate the objective conditions around them. Thus, there are no solely external, economic or political causalities or exclusively subjective motivations and reasons that lead to migration. When asking about the propensity to migrate or to stay, existential, contextual and conjectural factors need to be addressed and set out at the same time.

With this qualitative study (30 interviews with potential migrants and 6 interviews with key experts conducted from January to March 2021), we go beyond the traditional push-and-pull model of migration studies to improve our understanding as to why people decide to move. The majority of the interviewees come from the regions of Saint-Louis and Matam, and more specifically, from the rural villages and small towns (e.g., Ndioum, Ronkh, Kanel, Orkadiéré, Agnam Civol) along the course of the Senegal River. These areas of the middle and upper Senegal River valley, which are known for their agriculture, are also some of the territories most affected by climate change and environmental degradation. The sample also includes individuals from the regions in the Groundnut Basin, a historical area of out-migration: Diourbel, Thiès, Fatick and Kaolack. Some participants also originated from the region of Casamance, an area affected by security issues.

In line with previous studies, the collected data highlight how during the last decades international migration from Senegal has become highly generalized, today touching all strata of the working-age population. From a socio-professional point of view, along with students and former farmers and unemployed people, the majority of the interviewees were employed in the service sector (e.g., drivers, carters, gardeners, guardians) and the trade sector. A significant number of interviewees worked in the field of construction (e.g., bricklayers, carpenters, painters). Overall, it is worth underlining that whatever the professional sector, most of interviewees' employment conditions are shaped by informal contract terms. A greater diversification is also documented among the migratory profiles, in terms of gender and origins (almost all of the regions are affected by emigration, one such area being the Senegal River valley, as well as both rural and city dwellers), duration and place of residence (recently arrived in Dakar versus long-term residents), level of education (almost half of the interviewees have no education or only attended Koranic schools, while the remaining half only completed a primary or even lower level of education; very few have a higher level of education) and relationships with migrants living abroad.

In Senegal, among several ethnic groups, the movement of people within or beyond the country's borders is mostly a cultural phenomenon, the outcome of historical and socially shared values, practices and beliefs. The persistence of a particular "culture of migration" and a "Myth of Kaaw" (Sall, 2011) over the generations may explain why migration continues to occur even when in actual fact the context of destinations such as

Dakar has changed due to a progressive and significant decline in labour demand and, in terms of international migration, national and international political mechanisms are increasingly being implemented to curb the mobility of irregular migrants.

In parallel, the interviews with migrants and key experts have highlighted how the desire to move is triggered by the great difficulties in developing stable prospects in order to succeed socially (such as building a house or getting married) and the importance of economic factors (in particular, the limited opportunities offered by the agricultural sector and the lack of vocational training or job opportunities).

The interviews show that migration is a decision that often imposes itself. The willingness to improve individual livelihoods and the lives of relatives back in the places of origin appears to be the motivation shared equally by all of the interviewees. The challenging and chaotic urban context, the mixed and ambivalent feelings – swinging “from shame to ambition” (SenMig11) – underlying the migrants’ decision to move from rural areas to Dakar, appear to shape their different attitudes and propensities towards further mobility. However, it seems that potential international migrants are very often not necessarily in the situation of being able to choose whether to stay or to migrate. And when they decide to migrate the trajectories taken and the destinations chosen do not seem to correspond to a real project.

Although the migrants’ profiles have changed greatly over the last decades, most of the interviewees’ discourses confirm that Dakar is still the most attractive place of destination for people of rural origin, regardless their time of arrival, because it is the first accessible “visa-free” destination where there is a chance of improving their living conditions. The difficult economic and living conditions in the places of origin make migration to Dakar virtually inevitable and the only viable option.

Although environmental conditions and changes play an important role, as expressed in the interviews with the key experts, this aspect is not highlighted as a central issue by the potential migrants. Among the interviewees, environmental changes are not mentioned and apparently not perceived as a direct factor for migration. It does not yet seem possible to make an adequate empirical assessment of the social and environmental processes that may influence the decision to leave the areas of origin. Further research is needed to unravel the ambiguities of the relationship between environmental change and international migration. Against this background, the observations of one key expert give an interesting contribution, which is also in line with the one mentioned above, emphasizing that internal migration triggered by environmental changes does not usually lead to land abandonment, but to short-term mobility patterns.

Another issue that was frequently mentioned by the interviewees, in addition to the difficult economic situation and the general lack of jobs, is the lack of educational opportunities. The findings do not provide a clear explanation for the relationship between the type or level of education and the propensity to emigrate. Whether newcomers or long-term settlers, a central role in internal (as well as international) migration is played by relatives and friends, not only by providing initial accommodation in the capital, but also guidance and, less frequently, access to a first job.

Dakar still plays a role as a first step on the path to Europe. However, overpopulation, the reduced prospects of finding a job in the city, the tightening of policies restricting free movement as well as a complex mix of unfulfilled expectations and feelings (along the migration path) have led to an increasing nonlinearity and fragmentation of both the internal (e.g., temporary short-term migration practices) and international migration routes (e.g., unsuccessful migration attempts and impeded mobility).

As testified by several interviewees, the “urban experience” and the length of stay play an important role, forming a complex crossover which shapes the individuals’ evolving aspirations according to the conditions encountered. As a result, the specific social dynamics which occur within the urban context of Dakar prompt the coexistence of different migratory logics and trajectories. Thus, the migration mobility patterns which

have been documented in Dakar do not suggest a straightforward view of the capital as a stepping stone to international migration for migrants from rural areas.

The willingness to emigrate abroad via legal channels (especially to Europe or the United States), even on short notice if it were possible, is the dominant discourse of most of the interviewees. Only a limited number of interviewees expressed a preference to remain in Senegal. More generally, the migration propensity is mainly driven by a widespread experience of a lack of credible living prospects, combined with an increasing perception of living in a hostile environment. Overall, the evidence suggests that migration aspirations are higher among those people with low schooling and university graduates who are in a state of limbo in Dakar, working occasionally or waiting to find a decent job to earn a living. However, none of the interviewees had gathered the necessary information or had really planned the organization of the trip. Migration via a legal trajectory is perceived as an unattainable dream rather than a feasible and planned project.

With respect to both the migrants who recently arrived in Dakar and the long-term settlers, the findings of the qualitative interviews primarily suggest that it is not only difficult to separate the socio-cultural, economic and political factors underlying a migration decision but also that it is difficult to separate socio-cultural and economic factors from collective, individual or personal factors. Several of the interviewees highlight how migration is the outcome of more complex dynamics where individual initiative, family obligations and the reciprocity of relational duties within a family group are behind the decision to migrate.

Equally, the evidence demonstrates that very often no specific plans regarding a specific destination exist in the sense that the destination can change according to the opportunities at the time. Although most of the migration networks established with emigrants abroad (e.g., friends or relatives) draw trajectories that head to Europe, the potential destination countries of Senegalese migrants are very diverse, ranging from sub-Saharan Africa to North or South America, and more recently to East Asia.

In parallel, the search for alternative routes to reach Europe has been accompanied by a progressive informalization of migration initiatives (crossing the sea to the Canary Islands in pirogues or crossing the Sahara). Most interviewees are well aware of the dangers of these routes and the situation abroad. But in the face of a country that is neither able to guarantee economic development nor allows its citizens to advance socially and economically, people are much more afraid of social rather than physical death and of the difficulty of succeeding in the social environment in which they live or have lived. The general idea conveyed in the interviews is not so much a longing for a better place or for better opportunities, but the complete lack of opportunities in Senegal to earn a decent living, and thus the need to leave. And in the absence of the necessary means or contacts, irregular migration becomes the most popular option.

As such, the concrete implementation of the decision to migrate is rather the consequence of an unplanned opportunity, resulting from the availability of a migration network, coupled with fortuitous circumstances and heightened by the appeal of the visual and material evidence of the achievements of returnees that they see every day: the migrants have to “bide their time” (SenMig25).

Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated the socio-economic difficulties, triggering different, intertwined effects on the internal mobility of individuals towards the region of Dakar (one of the areas most affected by the pandemic) and making people even more likely to consider emigration than before. Interestingly, the discourses of several interviewees disclose a peculiar way of perceiving the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on Europe as a sign in favour of emigration inasmuch as the sudden death of many people results in the need for new workers. Far from being an isolated case, this view appears to be shared by several interviewees.

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

ADB African Development Bank

FAO Food and Agriculture Organization

IFAD International Fund for Agricultural Development

IOM-GMDAC International Organization for Migration's Global Migration Data Analysis Centre

IRD Institute of Research for Development

JRC Joint Research Centre

UNDESA United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division

WFP World Food Programme

